

Non-Thermal Plasma Approaches for Combating Implant-Associated Infections: A Compendious Review

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Abstract: Bacterial resistance to antibiotic therapy coupled with the propensity of microbes to develop highly recalcitrant biofilms on medical devices which are primary causes of implant failures. These infections necessitate complex revision surgeries and contribute to morbidity and mortality rates in healthcare. Despite the limitations inherent in various targeted sterilization approaches, non-thermal plasma (NTP) has emerged as a highly potent and versatile technology for the decontamination of medical device surfaces. In our review initially, we discussed comprehensively the implant surface physico-chemical attributes that cause the attachment of bacteria which advances to biofilms on the medical device surfaces. Our findings discuss various antimicrobial approaches, distinctly categorizing plasma interventions. Plasma surface modification (PSM) is highlighted for altering surface wettability and immobilizing antimicrobial agents. Furthermore, the review evaluates plasma-activated liquids (PAL) for their role in delivering reactive species to complex geometries. In contrast, direct NTP approaches emphasize the immediate gaseous-phase interaction of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS) with the device surface to achieve acute infection control. The review analyses the overall NTPs *in-vitro* studies mostly using plasma treated liquids and *in-vivo* by infiltration of ROS generating oxidative stress and DNA leakage from the cell walls as demonstrated efficiently against broad range of bacteria. The review concludes with the challenges such as standardization of plasma type and their process parameter.

1 **Keywords:** bacteria; biofilms; implants; infections; medical devices; non-thermal plasma,
2 sterilization.

3 4 **1. Introduction**

5 Medical implants are devices or tissues inserted on or within the living body's surface. Many
6 implants are prostheses designed to replace lost or rejected portions of the body as shown in [Figure 1](#).
7 A class of implants deliver drugs, evaluate or maintain organ and tissue activities in the body. Implants
8 are made of materials such as skin, bone, body tissues, metal, plastic, ceramic or other bio-compatible
9 materials. Implants can be permanently inserted or retrieved when no longer required. For instance,
10 stents or hip implants can be fixed permanently but damaged bones with fused chemical therapeutic ports
11 or screws can be removed when not required. Implants can weigh surgical risks while insertion or
12 extraction, like infections, mechanical failures, etc. During surgical process infections are involuntary
13 addition. Patients or operators contaminated skin, contaminated surgical devices, airborne microbes,
14 etc., are responsible for such infections. In the case of travelling implant infections, the site has to be
15 drained near the implant, administer antibiotics or remove the implant [1]. Nosocomial infections due
16 to wide spectrum of infecting microbes are one of the world's biggest challenges, one of the leading
17 causes of mortality in the world.

18 Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) are nosocomial infections symptoms are not visible at the
19 time of admission and is mostly found during a patient's hospital routine or related discharge stay.
20 These infections include central line-related bloodstream infections; surgical infections, urinary tract
21 infections associated with catheter, pneumoniae pathogen in the hospital; pneumonia associated with
22 the ventilator system and infections associated with *Clostridium difficile*, *Multi drug resistant*
23 *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus*, and
24 *Pseudomonas* species are among the most common bacteria associated with HAIs [2]. Diagnostic and
25 therapeutic procedures are the main causes of HAIs using infected medical devices. According to the
26 Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) in the US, in the course of treatment for other health
27 issues up to 1.7 million hospitalized US patients acquire HAI and more than 98,000 (one in 17) die
28 from HAIs. Out of total infections of HAIs - 32% are urinary tract infections, 22% are infections in
29 the surgical site, 15% are pneumonia infections, and 14% are infections in the bloodstream. The
30 demand for sterilization and disinfectant products is on the rise. The incidence of HAI depends
31 primarily on the patient's immune condition, infection control procedures, and the prevalence in
32 healthcare facilities of different infectious agents. Longer hospital stays, immunosuppression, the older
33 age and residence in intensive care units (ICUs) are other factors. Approximately 20% of these
34 infections are from ICUs. *C. difficile*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *E. coli* are

1 the most important pathogens causing HAIs [3]. The outbreak of COVID-19 as well as the increased
2 number of communal transmission cases identified in health care personnel (HCP) have led to the
3 implementation of guidelines on infection control by various government bodies worldwide [4].

4

5

6 Figure 1: Schematic showing examples of implant sites in human anatomy (Created using
7 Biorender.com).

8

9

1 As an alternative to the present manual techniques of surface disinfection, many novel
2 technologies are being developed and tested. These include the following:

- 3 • Water that has been electrolyzed (Hypochlorous acid)
- 4 • Low-pressure and atmospheric plasma
- 5 • Surfaces that self-disinfect
- 6 • Aerosol, vaporized hydrogen peroxide, and pulsed xenon ultraviolet (UV) light systems are
7 examples of no-touch decontamination.

8 These technologies are in various phases of research and testing, and they appear to be promising.
9 Reactive oxygen species (ROS) created by cold atmospheric plasma systems, for example, have shown
10 bactericidal action against many microorganisms in laboratory experiments with varying effectiveness
11 against *C. difficile* spores [5]. Stewart et.al., discovered that electrolyzed water significantly reduced
12 the number of aerobic bacteria (including *staphylococci*) on near-patient surfaces, but that it appeared
13 to allow *Staphylococci* to re-grow within 24 hours of application for unknown reasons. After use,
14 electrolyzed water does not leave hazardous residues on surfaces [6]. While commercializing such
15 technologies is difficult and expensive, they do provide potential alternatives. These technologies will
16 represent a serious challenge to the growth of existing techniques of surface disinfection, such as the
17 use of liquids and sprays, in the coming years, post-commercialization. The global market for infection
18 control has reached a worth US\$ 51 billion in 2024 and is estimated to grow with a compound annual
19 growth rate (CAGR) 6.3 % by 2032 to US\$ 65.4 billion [7]. Factors such as the high incidence of HIV
20 infections, the increasing number of surgical operations, the growing geriatric population and the
21 increased incidence of antibiotic resistance can be largely attributed to the growth of infection control
22 market [8].

23 A large number of research studies across the globe is pursuing to sterilize and control the
24 contaminated surfaces with biofilm using the well-known non-thermal plasma (NTP) method [8-10],
25 although very little work has been done on sterilizing the titanium surface with the biofilm that is
26 produced in a bioreactor in a dynamic state. NTP has numerous benefits, such as low cost and working
27 at or near room temperature, no usage of poisonous or hazardous gases and no release of harmful
28 radiation or residues [11]. The possibility of such studies can be imitated with the *in-vivo* environment
29 of the biofilm were growing in the bioreactor, just like an infected implant in the human body [12]. As
30 implant surface colonization by biofilm leads, recurrent surgery, replacement of the implant, etc. to
31 many infections and loss of medical costs [13]. The use of NTPs can thus be an effective way to prevent
32 infection and loss of medical costs. Various studies have helped in putting up a safe and effective

1 biofilm sterilization treatment technique and NTP has proved to be a potential antibacterial tool for
2 clinically treating biofilms.

3

4 **2. Necessity of implants**

5 An implant is a medical device that is designed to replace a missing biological component, sustain a
6 damaged biological structure, or improve a biological structure that already exists. In contrast to an
7 organ or tissue transplant, which is a transplanted biomedical tissue, medical implants are man-made
8 devices. Depending on which biomedical material is most functional, the surface of implants that
9 contact the body may be made of titanium, silicone, or apatite. Electronics are used in various implants,
10 such as artificial pacemakers and cochlear implants. Subcutaneous medication delivery devices in the
11 form of implantable tablets or drug-eluting stents are examples of bioactive implants [14,15].

12

13 **3. Device Materials Bulk and Surface Properties**

14 The selection of implant devices determines whether the materials used to make them are
15 appropriate for use in humans. Mechanical qualities that can withstand large loads are significant
16 criteria in the case of implants designed to replace bone tissue [14]. To limit thrombogenicity as much
17 as possible in blood vessel implants, the surface qualities, particularly the chemical composition and
18 physical morphology, are critical. On the other hand, if a material is utilized as a contact lens or
19 intraocular lens, optical transparency is obviously a crucial consideration for material selection [15, 16].
20 Aside from the material's biocompatibility, other characteristics such as sterilizability, required
21 physical strength, or a suitable sample capacity to process the material must be provided for an
22 implant material to be successful in use, as articulated in [Table 1](#) [17]. It is important to remember
23 that biocompatibility for implants is determined not only by the material's inherent qualities, but also
24 by the manufacturing process and any post-treatments such as sterilization. This means that, in the case
25 of polymers, a sterilizing procedure must be used that does not alter the material's bulk properties [16].

26

27 **Table 1: Bulk requirements of implants** [17].

28

Attribute	Expedients
Physical properties	Strength, elasticity, durability
Biocompatibility	Non-inflammatory, non-toxic, non-carcinogenic, non-pyrogenic, blood compatible, non-allergic

Sterilizability	Not destroyed by typical sterilizing techniques like autoclaving, dry heat, ethylene oxide, radiation
Manufacturability	Machinable, extrudable, moldable, printable

Aside from implants recommended biocompatibility, there is no universal set of criteria that, if met, designate a material as biocompatible. The length of time that a material is exposed to the human body must be taken into account. Table 2 illustrates some biomedical applications involving contact times with living organisms. It can be seen that, in the case of syringe needles, contact periods are relatively short, measured in seconds, implying that chemical reactivity or toxicity are not as important. The material suggestions for intraocular lenses or complete hip replacements when the desired time scale of contact with the host tissue is in the range of more than 15 years are substantially more varied [17]. One of the key requirements is to choose acceptable materials for a specific application based on these broad parameters for implant materials. Metals, ceramics, and polymers are the three main kinds of implant materials [18].

Table 2: Bulk and surface interaction timeline of implants (s = second) [17].

Implant	Duration
Syringe needle	1 – 2 s
Intraocular lens	>30 years
Total hip and joint replacement	10 – 15 years
Orthopaedic screw/plate	3 – 12 months
Ocular lens	12 h to 30 days
Tongue depressor	10 s

Surface-determined variables such as biocompatibility and corrosion resistance are important in achieving a high level of compatibility of a material system with the host tissue. These surface characteristics have an indirect influence on mechanical behavior such as stress shielding, wear debris, and fatigue failure. Most significantly, when the synthetic device's surface comes into close contact with the human anatomy, the surface of a material system must be given special consideration, as its response with the host tissue is often the deciding factor in implantation success or failure. Surface properties that affect the host tissue's reactivity include surface energy [19], wettability [20], roughness,

1 chemical composition, electrical charge, crystallinity, and mobility. In many situations, atomic
2 composition near the surface is very unstable, but they control the most of the biological processes at
3 the bacteria-implant interface. The surface of the implant might be made up of individual atoms,
4 molecules, crystallographic patterns, or massive polymeric structures, depending on the implant
5 material. Surfaces are made up of molecules or atoms having dangling or strained bonds that aren't
6 fully saturated. Surface atoms are less bound, resulting in increased mobility and reactivity of the
7 species. As a result, phase transitions, crystallization, and corrosion (dissolution) processes are all
8 possible for these surface atoms. In the case of adsorbates from the biological system, the increased
9 energy and reactivity are especially relevant. When a surface like this comes into touch with the
10 microbes, it instantly responds by forming new bonds and compounds, increasing the surface energy
11 [21]. The number of atoms in the "surface" state is restricted to a few atomic layers, in contrast to the
12 extensive arrangement of atoms in the bulk state of materials. This necessitates the use of specialized
13 characterization techniques. Surface phenomena are largely caused by a decrease in surface free energy
14 combined with increased chemical reactivity. Specific points will be briefly discussed in the following
15 sections.

17 3.1 Surface Segregation and Reconstruction

18 Even in the absence of a specific environment, surfaces have the potential to spontaneously
19 change their structure and chemistry. Surface segregation and reconstruction are some of them. The
20 most basic definition of surface segregation is the redistribution of solute atoms between a material's
21 surface and bulk in order to reduce the overall energy of the substance. As a result, even with single-
22 crystal surfaces in vacuum, surface reconstruction is frequently observed. In the simplest instance, the
23 atoms in the outermost layer rearrange to reduce the overall surface energy. While reconstruction can
24 result in periodic nanoscopic surface patterns, no interaction with biomedically important species has
25 been observed to our knowledge. Surface segregation effects are more physiologically meaningful.

26 Surface segregation is an interfacial adsorption phenomenon that involves a bulk component
27 of a multi-component material, resulting in a compound environment at the surface. Metallic materials
28 usually have several phases at the microscopic level. For example, Ti6Al4V is a frequently used
29 orthopaedic implant material that is made up of two phases: an aluminum-rich α -phase and a
30 vanadium-rich β -phase. The chemical makeup of not only these various phases, but also the grain
31 boundaries, may change. Grain-boundary diffusion and mobility, as well as surrounding impacts like

1 as intergranular corrosion and stress corrosion cracking, are further examples of surface segregations
2 in inorganic biomedical materials [22]. Segregation of macromolecular chains at the surface of polymers
3 can result in a variety of microstructural domains. Proteins may interact differently with each phase,
4 depending on the chemical species present within these domains [23]. Surface segregations' relevance
5 in biomedical applications can be characterized in terms of localized toxicity, decreased corrosion
6 resistance, or, in the case of the adsorption processes mentioned above, changed protein or cell
7 adhesivity in the host tissue.

8 Surface chemistries and structures can alter in response to an external factor as a consequence
9 of surface segregation and other influencing variables in order to minimize interfacial tension.
10 However, sufficient atomic or molecular mobility must exist to allow for surface changes in an
11 acceptable amount of time [24]. An implant surface may have patches or domains of different
12 functionalities at the microscopic level, allowing newly formed surface chemistry to migrate from the
13 surface into the bulk, or molecules from the bulk to diffuse or interdiffuse and thus rearrange among
14 themselves or with surrounding species [25] in metallic and other inorganic systems as well as polymer
15 systems, such reversals take place. Polymers can also undergo reorientation in the outermost layers by
16 switching from dry air to wet air in the surrounding environment. Therefore, impacts of surface
17 separation are commonly employed to characterize changes in surface and chemistry linked to
18 mobility. Actually, if a changed surface remains in the designated condition, surface reversal must be
19 prevented or hindered.

20 3.2 Surface Charge

21 The origin of the charge located on a firm surface can either be caused by the loading balance
22 with the surrounding, contact, or by an inherent fault in the surface (e.g. space loading layers in
23 semiconductor connections). The first scenario is based on the charge for two media in contact, that is,
24 if a metal, semiconductor or insulator is in touch with a second phase (material), the FERMI-level of
25 two phases is balanced and generally leads to loaded surfaces (the chemical potential). For metals, the
26 characteristic charges for contacts with fluids are often a double layer (Helmholtz-layer), where a
27 spatial charge layer is formed for semiconductors and insulators, which extends to the solid material
28 considerably [26]. Another origin of charges is the interrupted surface crystal structure – i.e. on the
29 surface, the unsaturated links (dangling bonds) contribute to charge.

1 Stress on solid surfaces must be balanced by solution species. In the solutions, the main carriers
2 of loads must be regarded or can even become dominant for solvated species, such as colloids or
3 proteins. The overall description of the contribution to the surface potential of a given solution species
4 generally is as follows:

$$\Delta\mu_i = \frac{RT}{z \ln \frac{C_i}{C_i^{PZC}}} \dots\dots(1)$$

6 where in equation 1, the C_i^{PZC} represents the concentration at the point of zero charge (PZC), C_i the
7 normal concentration and $\Delta\mu_i$ the chemical potential.

8 The PZC or the isoelectric point reflects the scenario for colloids (protein solutions) in equation
9 1 above, when no net charges can be detected microscopically [27]. Surface stress loads encourages
10 external load adsorption. As proteins carry substantial burdens in a biological context, significant
11 studies on relating surface charging phenomena to the interactions of surface proteins have been
12 conducted.

13 3.3 Adsorption Phenomena

14 Adsorption phenomena are often divided in physisorption processes on the fluid-solid
15 interface [28]. The surface energy, i.e. charge presence at interfaces, is the basis of molecules
16 physisorption at interfaces. The origin of the space charge layers may be localized load, for example,
17 by semiconductors, or by the induced weak van der Waals forces, including oxides like TiO_2 or Fe_2O_3 .
18 Last comes from the time when an adsorbate induces in a surface (interaction with its own image
19 charge). This contact energy can be modest (beyond 10^3 mJ/m^3), yet it makes a major contribution to
20 solid surface interaction with micromolecules.

21 Chemisorption takes into account the development of a strong covalent bond on the surface in
22 its original concept (in other words, a chemical surface reaction to take place). One example most
23 commonly involves surface hydroxide groups, which react under H_2O division with an anchoring
24 molecule (e.g. $R-COOH$, $R-NH_2$, $R-SiOH$). It is frequently utilized for bonding organic material to
25 surface oxides. The kinetic interaction of a certain degree of surface mobility between the pure generated
26 dipoles and the creation of chemical bonds is still possible. In other words, in this situation, a tight
27 distinction between chemisorption and physisorption is often not possible.

28 In principle, physisorption is reversible, either on the adsorbate or on the surface, without any
29 chemical changes, while chemisorption is an irreversible chemical adsorption. The molar adsorption
30 enthalpy may be obtained between -5 and -40 kJ/mol for physisorption, whereas chemisorption leads
31 to molar adsorption enthalpy levels of around -200 to -800 kJ/mol [29]. Surfaces of higher energy are
32 generally coated or doped with lower energy species from an analysis point the surface science.

1 In general, a certain molecule can physisorb and chemisorb on the same surface. More
2 specifically, a molecule can first be physisorbed and transformed into a chemisorbed state. A
3 combination of physisorbed and chemisorbed molecules on the surface is a typical equilibrium
4 condition, dependent on the availability of appropriate surface locations^[30]. Adsorption on surfaces is
5 generally described by so-called isotherms^[31], which are mostly based on experimental data and which
6 usually contain semi-empirical parameters. The Langmuir isotherm is the most common approach as
7 mentioned in equation 2 below:

$$\Theta = \frac{KP}{1+KP} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

8 where in equation (2), P is the partial pressure, Θ is the coverage (number of adsorption sites
9 occupied/available) (for gases or molecular concentration in liquid).

10
11 Given the excessive simplification of this technique, a variety of more sophisticated procedures
12 for the desorption and adsorption (BET or Kisliuk) have been developed. The study linked to
13 observations on self-assembled monolayers may be especially remarkable in the context of microbes.
14 The crucial assumption that Langmuir Isotherms do not interfere with the adsorption process of a
15 neighbouring adsorbial species was highly valid at low surface concentrations, it has been found that
16 the molecules tend to adsorb, but at high concentrations certain ionic interactions of components in
17 the molecule force change over into a "stepped" configuration (presumably as determined by the van
18 der Waals forces), these effects are explained, e.g. by the Kisliuk isothermal type^[32].

19 In view of the important surfaces that are devoted to inserting into the human body, it is necessary
20 for future biological performance to include ion adsorption of bodily fluids (e.g. Ca- and phosphate
21 ions) as well as adsorption of biomolecules (e.g. proteins). Depending on the surface characteristics
22 (chemistry, charges, energy), adsorption behavior of various species may be adjusted by certain surface
23 changes. With regard to protein adsorption, hydrophilic material displays a lower interface energy
24 compared to hydrophobic ones in a water-based environment. This indicates that the hydrophobic
25 surface adsorption characteristic of proteins may get denatured. In reality, the hydrogen bonding
26 groups move towards the water, whereas the hydrophobic groups tend to be more hydrophobic^[17]. As
27 a result of these phenomena of thermodynamic adhesion, adherence for bovine serum albumin was
28 shown to be greatest in intermediate hydrophilic conditions on surfaces with different weathering
29 conditions between superhydrophobic and superhydrophilic^[33].

30 Protein adsorption phenomena are specifically related to the fact that the protein can alter its
31 shape after the surface has been adsorbed^[34]. The surrounding electrolyte may not be exposed to
32 hydrophobic parts in aqueous solutions (energetically not favored). However, when the protein "finds"

1 hydrophobic surfaces or surface location, the maximum contact between both interfaces might be
2 energetically advantageous - therefore, changes in surface-induced shape or the denaturation of
3 proteins could occur. Protein surfaces are also usually bipolar, so that either hydrophilic or
4 hydrophobic surfaces might coincide preferably with the surface or a certain surface site. Because of
5 this uncertainty, the adsorption isotherms are frequently followed simply in kinetics rather than by a
6 measurement of the equilibrium protein level in accordance with the solution concentration [35].
7 Different *in situ* surface sensitive techniques, for example, ellipsometry, can be employed to track
8 kinetics, reflectometry, infrared spectroscopy, Raman dispersion, circular dichroism, emission of
9 fluorescence or resonance of the plasmon surface, are most prevalent nowadays. For example, there
10 were several reviews of similar approaches [36].

11 **4. Biofilm and Its Growth**

12 **4.1 Biofilm**

13 Identification of biofilms on medical devices has been carried out in investigations where the
14 items have either been evaluated or tested in animal research facilities systems after removal from
15 the patients. Raad et al. employed the electron scanning microscope to prove that biofilms have
16 universally colonized the central venous catheters that were removed from the patients [37]. These and
17 other researchers have also employed cultural medium and other processing approaches to extract,
18 grow and quantify organisms from medical equipment blanked with biofilm [38-41]. In order to eliminate
19 biofilm aggregations from the device surface, Tunney et al. investigated prosthetic hip prostheses using
20 a sonication method. In order to study these biofilm aggregates and record the existence of biofilms
21 on the device surface, the confocal laser scanning microscope was utilized. Documenting biofilms
22 (called 'vegetations') occurring on mechanical and prosthetic heart valves was employed in other
23 imaging methods including echocardiography [43].

24 **4.2 Biofilm Formation**

25 In the last few years, biofilms have been widely investigated, and the mechanisms of microbial
26 adhesion and the early development of biofilm is well documented. The structure of the substrata and
27 the cell surface must be carefully examined in order to understand the attachment in the early stage of
28 biofilm development. Teflon (DuPont), silicone, and latex are examples of extremely hydrophobic
29 materials. They range in degree from hydrophilicity to highly integrated hydrophilic materials, such
30 as the surfaces of glass and other metals. Some materials, such as metal pipes made of copper or
31 copper-based alloys, catheters impregnated with antibiotics, and sewing rings for heart valves, are also

1 antimicrobial. The substratum's properties can significantly affect microorganisms' rates and degree of
 2 fixation. Although exceptions exist, biofilms are often produced on rougher and more hydrophobic
 3 surfaces [44]. The problem gets more difficult if we consider that every substratum put in a fluid
 4 environment (whether the bloodstream, or the urinary catheter line) obtains a conditioning film or
 5 coating consisting largely of the fluid's protein. This layer provides the surface of the substratum with
 6 chemical characteristics that can hide the qualities of the underlying substratum itself. The features of
 7 the cell surface are also significant, in addition to the substratum characteristics. For instance, flagella,
 8 pili, fimbria or glycocalyx might affect microbial attachment rates. For instance, the microbial cell
 9 must, once attract to the surface, resist the repulsive forces inherent to all materials, which allow the
 10 cell to stay connected until more permanent fixing processes are in place, shown in Figure 2. Korber
 11 et al. examined mutant and wild-type organisms and found that the existence of flagella made it
 12 possible for bacteria to adhere to surfaces, gram-negative [45]. Research revealed the significance of
 13 attachment of fimbriae (which are exterior bacterial protein structures) [46]. The hydrophobicity of the
 14 cell surface has also been highly crucial to the binding to surfaces [47].

15 Figure 2. Schematic formation of biofilm on a plant surface (a) exhibiting reversible phases of bacteria
 16 showing, Motility => adhesion, (b) exhibiting irreversible phases of surface adhered bacteria formed
 17 biofilm showing, Maturation => Dispersion => Propagation, (c) anatomy of biofilm forming
 18 bacterium. Figure (a) created using servier smart art, figure (b) and (c) created using Biorender.com.

20 4.3 Biofilm growth

21 The cells that fix themselves irreversibly to surfaces (those not removed by mild rinsing)
 22 continue to divide cells; which create microcolonies. These extracellular polysaccharides (EPSs)
 23 mostly consist of polymeric materials and may be microscopically identified and analyzed. The matrix
 24 or structure of the biofilm is formed by EPSs. They are hydrated (98% water) and are tightly attached
 25 to the surface underneath it. The structure of a biofilm is not only a homogeneous slime monolayer,
 26 but is heterogeneous, in place and in time, with "water channels" which permit the transmission of

1 vital nutrients and oxygen into the biofilm of the cells [48]. Biofilms tend to function as filters for
2 trapping particles of many types, including fibrin, RBCs, platelets, and other minerals and host
3 components. Biofilm-associated organisms grow more slowly, possibly because the cells are
4 constrained by the depletion of food and/or oxygen [49]. As a result of the development and division of
5 cells or the elimination of biofilm aggregates including cell masses, cells separate from the biofilm.
6 Depending upon a variety of circumstances, including the reaction of the host immune system, these
7 detachable cells can produce and propagate a systemic infection.

9 4.4 Accumulation and Maturation

10 The attachment of the bacteria on an implant surface is followed by several processes wherein
11 bacteria are replicated and recruited and extracellular polymer products in many distinct layers of the
12 microbe are formed. The mature matrix of the biofilm is formed in this way. Additional adaptation of
13 bacteria adhering to the surface focuses on enhanced production and development of antimicrobial
14 resistance properties of extracellular polymer molecules. The mature biofilm also has enhanced genetic
15 exchange information, UV tolerance, and enhanced metabolic synthesis [50].

16 Biofilms have significant links to the existence of the *ica* gene operon and maturation happens
17 in gram-positive *Staphylococci* species. Although not necessary for the development of biofilms, the
18 *ica* gene operon is responsible for producing intercellular adhesion polysaccharide and slime-
19 associated extracellular antigen [51]. The *ica* gene cluster has been demonstrated to possess 85% of *S.*
20 *Epidermidis* strains in infectious blood cells [52]. Extracellular antigen slime-related is chemically
21 similar to PLGA but with antigenic variations that arise in the main substituent present for amino groups,
22 and the 1,6-related polyglucosamine backbone [53]. Slime-associated antigen plays a significant role in
23 the formation and deposition of biofilms, whereas capsular polysaccharide adhesion is linked to
24 adhesivity. The locus *ica* gene may be further characterized as *icaADBC* biosynthetic locus and *icaR*.
25 The gene locus *icaR* genes for a transcriptional controller that is connected to the *icaADBC* promoter,
26 which regulates *icaADBC* negatively. In controlling the development, adhesion and virulence of a
27 biofilm, the relevance of *icaADBC* gene operons have been shown by the incorporation of an
28 *icaRADBC* sequence into biofilm-forming *S. epidermidis* strains [54].

29 The regulation of *icaR* transcription in *S. epidermidis* shall be governed by the alternative sigma
30 factor σ^B , which, by activating environmental factors, such as the shock of heat, acid, salt or ethanol,
31 osmolarity, glucose, oxygen deficiency and antibiotics positively regulates the protein RsbU [55]. The
32 creation of factor σ^B indirectly represses the transcription of the *icaR* operon, which enables the

1 formation of biofilm by a synthesis of intercellular polysaccharide adhesion and slim-associative
2 extracellular antigen. For the manufacture of PIA and thus biofilm growth, *S. aureus* relies more on
3 the relatively unequalled staphylococcal accessory regulator A protein [56]. The *icaADBC* operon is
4 binding and positively regulating with *S. epidermidis* [57] via an *icaR* independent mechanism [58]. As
5 with RsbU, the *Staphylococcal* accessory regulator protein A found mostly on *S. epidermidis* is
6 positively regulated by environmental stressors such as increased levels of salt, ethanol and iron [59].
7 The synthesis of B also favorably affects the *Staphylococcal* accessories regulator protein A [60]. The
8 accumulation and maturation of the biofilm, associated with the gram-negative bacteria *P. aeruginosa*
9 and *E. coli*, correlates to the increasing synthesis of the polymeric alginate and colanic acid [61]. Both
10 chemicals generate a biofilm architecture although they are not required for development of biofilm.
11 The three-dimensional architectural structure of *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* is comparable to the majority
12 of biofilms with the presence of water canals, macro-colonies with substantial heterogeneity and a
13 thick matrix. On the surface of the material a bacterial monolayer develops after the first adherence of
14 *P. aeruginosa*.

15 The movement by extending and shrinking type IV pili bacteria over the surface continues by
16 tweaking motility [62,63]. Building migration leads to the top part of the mushroom formations in *P.*
17 *aeruginosa* biofilms and depends on type IV pili. Bimolecular alterations in the gram-negative
18 species depend upon motility-related genes and the synthesis of extracellular polymers occurring
19 through down-regulation [65] in particular through the use of flagella-related genes. The aggregation,
20 the maturation and the creation of biofilm architectures in non-mucoid *P. aeruginosa*-related medical
21 equipment are mainly caused by the manufacture of Psl and Pel exopolysaccharides. The PslA-O and
22 PelA genes are encoded in the well characterized strain *P. aeruginosa* (PAO1) in proteins,
23 enzymes and transporting molecules, which are necessary for the manufacture of Psl and Pel and
24 pili (thin coil surrounding biofilms that build at the Air-Liquid Interface) [66]. Some strains, such
25 as the PAO1 isolate, lack the gene locus *pslA-G* [67]. Pel is a glucose-rich polymer that has been shown
26 to be present in all known *P. aeruginosa* strains [68] with genes regulating its synthesis (Pel). Psl is
27 found predominantly in the outer areas of the biofilm matrix and can help attract free-flowing plankton
28 bacteria that increase bacterial aggregation and contribute to the overall structure of the biofilm [61]. In
29 biofilm development and stabilization, extracellular DNA also plays a major role. The extracellular
30 matrix of *P. aeruginosa* (PAO1) with exopolysaccharides of high relevance in relation to its structural
31 integrity was proven to be the most common polymer by Matsukawa and Greenberg [69]. *E. Coli* biofilm
32 maturation, combined with colanic acid production, is increased by genes linked with OmpC porin and
33 *wca* locus. The *fliC* gene needed for flagella biogenesis is, in contrast, decreased [70].

1 Colanic acid is a compound made up of high fucose and glucuronic acid sub-units [71]. Colanic
2 acid synthesis and its negative impact allow *E. coli* biofilms to survive great variations in osmotic
3 stress, oxidative stress (via hydrogen peroxide) and temperature due to their physical barrier [72]. The
4 bacterial maturation in either of these gram-negative bacteria, together with the long-chain
5 hydrocarbon structures derived from fatty acids, acidified ester, peptides, α -butyrolactones, 2-alkyl-
6 4-quinolones, furanones and derivatives from 4,5-dihydroxy-2,3-pentandione, is tightly controlled
7 through quorum-sensing systems of N-acyl-L-homoserine lactone as signaling molecules [73,74].
8

9 **4.5 Dispersion and recolonization**

10 To recolonize infection-free new surfaces, dispersion from biofilms is crucial for the
11 transmission of both the primary source infection, for example, the environment, and the spread of the
12 host illness [75,76]. The microbial population suffers from a shortage of nutrients and the rise in toxic
13 waste products as the biofilm life cycle reaches the lagging phase of its growth. These environmental
14 variables are associated with an increased density and biomass of the biofilm population over
15 sustainable values. Thus, genetically planned to search for new surfaces to colonize and re-enter the
16 biofilm formation process in order to thrive and form other biofilm cells. Different dispersion
17 techniques exist, and no one method is used by all microbial species. The process is not characterized
18 by the production of biofilms but is nonetheless crucial in the whole cycle of biofilm life. Biofilm cell
19 dispersal might occur by physical removal of microbes from the biofilm ultrastructure using
20 hydrodynamic forces. The principal methods involved include sloughing, abrasion and erosion,
21 including predator pastures and human intervention [77]. Passive biofilm dispersal is considered to be
22 physical removal.

23 Abrasion and erosion include a physical removal of biofilms by shear forces or divisions of the
24 cell, erosion for direct physical force, as a collision with the surrounding media by particulate matter,
25 of single cells or tiny colonies of cells less than 25 μm in diameter [79]. Sloughing is a more random
26 procedure, which occurs in thicker and portion-loss bio-films with no nutrients and oxygen or a rapid
27 rise in shear pressure than erosion or abrasion [78]. The possibility is for abrasion, erosion and
28 sloughing to generate scattered cells that maintain biofilm-type features, such as antibacterial
29 capabilities. The importance of biofilm dispersal is the possibility of increasing the already existent
30 infection profile of medical devices, or making it possible for the infection to move rapidly to other
31 regions. Dispersion is complicated by multiple effectors, signal transduction, and environmental
32 signals [76].

1 Dispersal has different separation stages, translocalization and a new surface connection. The
2 essence of a subpopulation of peripheral biofilm cells is genotypically modified to return to the
3 planktonic organism. Genes related to motility annexes are increased, for example, in genes connected
4 to exopolysaccharide production and accumulation, there is a corresponding down-regulation^[80]. This
5 is an example of an active dispersion mechanism in which the bacteria themselves begin the process
6 of separation. In order to disrupt the outer parts of the extracellular matrix, it is essential to produce
7 proteases to release the planktonic colonizing cells. Enzymes which breakdown biofilm matrix in cell
8 separation, which allow glycosidases, proteases and deoxyribonucleases to be released into the
9 environment, are also supported in this way. For instance, alginate lyase is related to alginate digestion
10 and algL is the primary component of *P. aeruginosa* biofilms mucoid^[81].

11 Mann et. al., have shown that the breakdown of extracellular DNA, a major adhesive of *S.*
12 *aureus* biofilms, is a deoxyribonucleases micrococcal nuclease or the mononuclease^[82]. Others include
13 *S. epidermidis* hyaluronidase and *E. coli* N-acetyl-heparosanase^[83]. Enzymes are also involved in
14 the dispersion from the biofilm structure of substantial portions of interior microcolonies, an active
15 process called seeding^[84]. The formation, which is highly related to the transfer of the enzymes from
16 across the cellular membrane in the extracellular polysaccharide matrix by lysis of bacterial cells inside
17 the biofilm matrix, of large hollow holes were seen in *P. aeruginosa* strains^[85,86]. It is also proven to
18 be helpful with bacterial dispersion through decreased cell surface and cell-cell contacts due to their
19 surface-like characteristics because extracellular amphipathic surfactor molecules are generated by
20 bacteria. Rhamnolipids are a rhamnose molecule that is connected with 3-hydroxy fatty acids by β -
21 glycosidic bonds, and is made in *P. aeruginosa*^[87]. Examples are the synthesis of L- rhamnosyl-3-
22 hydroxyacyl-3-hydroxydecanoate and the rhaAB operon overexpression^[88]. The quorum-sensing
23 system of agritoxin in *S. aureus* is linked to the production of the surfactant-like molecule of D-toxin
24 that can help disperse biofilms^[89]. But also proteases (Aur, SplABCDEF, ScpA, Staphylococcus Serine
25 Protease 3B) that are suitable for surface adhesives such as Microbial Surface Components
26 Recognizing Adhesive Matrix Molecules (MSCRAMM) and surface protein autolysin^[90]. N -acyl-l-
27 homoserine lactone involved in quorum sensing in *P. aeruginosa* in gram-negative microorganisms
28 regulating biofilm formation and dispersion by quorum sensing^[91].

30 **5. The Material Surface – Bacteria Interaction**

31 Bacteria may be found before or after implantation of a medical device. The probability of
32 bacterial adherence depends on the device and bacterium surface properties and the process kinetics,
33 such as hydrodynamics on the surface with implanted equipment^[92], which are governed by the
34 environment (kinetics) of the process. An implant is the host to a range of host biomolecules, including

1 as Fibronectin, Fibrinogen, Collagen and other extracellular matrix (ECM) components, which fouls
2 the surface of most devices [93]. This suggests the surface of cells, including planktonic bacteria, for
3 further coupling. Free-floating bacteria have the impact of physical forces such as Brownian motion,
4 van der Waals attraction forces, gravity forces, and the influence of electrostatic surface induces
5 hydrophobic interactions on the implant surface [94]. In order to answer chemical and physical
6 questions, bacteria not only move passively, but they may also show purposeful motility, including
7 swimming or swarming [95]. Sensing a chemoattractor like an amino acid, polysaccharide or
8 oligopeptide encourages a cell to move into it in frequent flows; whereas diminishing attractant
9 concentrations and/ or rising repellent levels like severe pH, metal ions or hydrophobic amino acids
10 can lead to cell tumbling. After implantation, bacterial adherence is required, as demonstrated for *S.*
11 *aureus* fibrinogen and recommended for *S. epidermidis*, by unique ligand receptor interaction [96].
12 Strong, long-range electrostatic forces often dominate such sticky interactions (Figure 3). Further
13 stability of adhesive bonding can produce short-range interactions such as hydrogen bonding.
14 Nonspecific interactions may occur with devices before implantation or with biomaterials adsorbed by
15 proteins and/or biological components [97]. It includes attractive van der Waals and hydrophobic
16 contacts, which dominate non-covalent physical forces.

17 The success of approaching the surface of the bacterium depends heavily on its physico-
18 chemical qualities such as surface properties and how they connect with the device surface,
19 respectively. A combination of surface hydrophobicity, free surface energy and micro topography of
20 the substrates either facilitates or impedes the adhesion of bacteria. The irreversible, molecular or cell
21 phase of adhesion is followed by reversible association. When the distance between the cells and
22 surface is below 5 nm, the chemical interactions between bacterial surface features (e.g. capsules,
23 fibrillae, pili, and slime, ionic and dipole interactions), hydration and/or hydrophobic contacts, are
24 strong enough to permit permanent attachment (Figure 3). Adhering cells multiply fast and create a
25 range of extracellular chemicals and structures to further stabilize their attachment and construct a
26 highly organized three-dimensional biofilm [98].

27 The surface physicochemical properties and the components of the surrounding medium (such
28 as pH, ionic force, etc.) [99] and the local hemodynamic circumstances prevail at the interfaces are
29 affected by many factors [100]; the surface-like physicochemical characteristics of the biomaterials (such
30 as the chemical makeup), surface energy and charge [101,102], the bacteria [103]. The intermolecular forces
31 over the interfacial field of close contact are cumulative and can produce a very strong adhesive bond.
32 In addition, topography and the design of implant surfaces will play a critical role in determining
33 adherence of the bacteria, especially if the blood is turbulent [104]. Besides the aforementioned
34 interactions with bacteria and areas, chemical sensing has an essential function to play in biofilm-

1 related cell recruitment by controlling the production of cellular components and sensing bacteria ^[105].
2 The significance of mechanical indicators in the movement of fixed bacteria throughout the surface is
3 less recognized. Due to the limits of existing imaging technologies and/or the paucity of research in
4 the field, it is conceivable that these mechanisms were not found. Indeed, the interaction of physical
5 and chemical processes in the driving of cell migration for eukaryotic cells was only characterized
6 recently. And while this interaction is recognized as a major component for gradient sensing,
7 cytoskeletal dynamics, signal transduction, polarization and directed migration, there are ambiguous
8 responses to various directions ^[106]. Microorganisms within the biofilm community have a varying
9 range of multicellular behavioral complexities, including quorum sensing, sharing of nutrient-
10 scavenging molecules ^[107]. This can lead to the development of collective migration. When the microbe
11 colonizes the surface, highly coherent groups of bacteria move through the semi-solid medium
12 surface on the border of the biofilm, creating grooves that preferably migrated swimming cells. The
13 extracellular DNA was designed to enable highly coordinated mass cells transit through a
14 comprehensive network of linked pathways towards the top corner of the film, ensure coherent cell
15 alignment and maintain a steady supply of cells to the migrating front. The extracellular DNA was a
16 traffic controller. Such an organization in the biofilm community not only allows for a high metabolic
17 efficiency, but also integrates biofilm residential bacteria with the ability to tolerate high antibiotic
18 doses and to withstand environmental changes ^[108]. Long-range surface interactions between bacteria
19 and implants include electrostatic forces, bacterial location near the surface, and forces outlined in the
20 (Deraguin, Landau, Verwey, Overbeek) DLVO theory of the Van der Waals ^[109]. In the near-surface
21 (~2 to 3 nm) area, bacterial interactions with the surface may prevail via the hydrophobic effect and
22 associated interactions. Directed contact between structures on the bacterial surface and the device
23 causes solid adherence in time-dependent fashion, following or concurrent to physiochemical
24 attachment (> 1 to 3 h) ^[110].

25 Bacterial and fimbrial capsules are bacterial adhesives that connect the bacteria to the surface
26 of the substrate via contact through non-specific hydrophobic, electrostatic and/or ligand-receptor
27 specific interactions (Figure 3). Some *S. epidermidis* strains generate extracellular slime
28 polysaccharides that can enhance the binding of bacteria to surfaces ^[111]. Initially, bacteria near the
29 surface of the aqueous medium interact at a secondary minimum energy that permits bacteria to
30 migrate laterally along a device surface. Attractive interactions (e.g. hydrophobic) or bridging the
31 separation gap with outstretched fibrillary adhesives on the bacterial surface allow for the minimal
32 primary energies, which allows for intimate contact between bacteria and the implant surface. For
33 these two processes, hydrophobic effects are required to remove the water layer(s) between bacteria
34 and the material surface. Hydrophobic interactions are very prominent in aquatic media and decay

1 exponentially with separation distance (D) which are around 1 - 2 nm of decay length between 0 - 10
2 nm ^[112]. In the domain from 0 to 10 nm, the hydrophobic energy interaction (W_{HI}) is represented by:

3
$$W_{HI}(D) = 2\gamma_1 \exp\left(-\frac{D}{\lambda_0}\right) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

4 Where in equation 3, the typical potential long decay is when γ_1 is the water-interfacial energy and λ_0
5 is the distance (1 to 2 nm).

6 Because hydrophobic interactions can be considerably greater at short distances (less than 5
7 nm) than electrostatic or van der Waals forces, the magnitude of nonspecific bacterial adhesion is
8 predicted to have an essential role to play. A negative decrease in Helmholtz free adhesion energy
9 (G_{adh}) shows thermodynamic adhesion conditions as follows:

10
$$G_{adh} = \gamma_{bs} - \gamma_{sl} - \gamma_{bl} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

11 where in equation 4, γ_{bs} , γ_{sl} , and γ_{bl} are the bacterium-substrate, substrate and bacterial median
12 interfacial free energies respectively ^[113].

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1
2
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Figure 3: Graphical representation of bacterial interaction with surface (Created using Biorender.com).

1 In the measurement of contact angles and application of the Young-Dupres equation, interfacial
 2 energy and adhesive work may be calculated. In physiological circumstances, bacteria carry a net
 3 negative surface burden, leading to further repellent or attracting electrostatic interactions with a
 4 loaded solid surface. Therefore, positive charged surfaces are predicted to encourage greater adherence
 5 of microbes. However, in aqueous buffer environments, the effects are minimized since charges are
 6 protected from solvent counter ions of opposite charge on the surface of bacteria or implants [114].
 7 This produces a double layer on each surface of the biofilm (Stern and diffuse). The effective distance
 8 of interaction relies on the thickness of the double layer calculated from the Debye length and the
 9 characteristics of the medium (e.g., ionic strength, pH, and electrolyte type). The adherence forces of
 10 bacteria may be measured under controlled laminar flow circumstances by analyzing variations in
 11 the forces leading to increased dissociation (e.g. decreased adhesion). The uneven flow rate over the
 12 top and bottom sections of the bacterium generates an elevating force (FL) in the body of the forces
 13 created by the flow field [114]. This distribution of force works to remove a particle off the surface.

$$FL = (81.2) \mu u^2 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z}\right)^{0.5} v^{-0.5} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

15 where in equation 5, a is particle radius, u is the speed, $\delta u/\delta z$ is the speed gradient; μ is the fluid
 16 viscosity, and v is the kinematic fluid viscosity. A lift force (FL) acts in the direction of flow, slightly
 17 above its centre, because of the friction force of the fluid moving across the particle.

$$FL = 6\pi\mu u a f \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

19 Where in equation 6, “a” coefficient is equal to $\pi/16$ and is dimensionless [115].

20 As a consequence, sometimes the unequal distribution of force is applied to the bacteria. This
 21 pair tends to spin the particle towards the direction of the flow and has the magnitude: $8\pi\mu a^2 g$, where
 22 g is equal to 0.44 [115]. This study is valid for relatively low Reynolds laminar flow conditions. Any
 23 contact between cells and surfaces must thus create a sufficient attractive force to stop the cell's spin
 24 before shedding occurs. If this analysis is for leukocyte instead of a bacterium, the well-known
 25 phenomenon of the 'leukocyte rolling' phenomenon that is found under laminar physiological flow
 26 circumstances is mathematically reflected [116]. Similarly, we may include the increase in leukocytes'
 27 susceptibility to applied shear stress in comparison with bacteria. To maintain a surface attachment of
 28 a bacterium and/or cells, sufficient (specific and/or nonspecific) adhesive force needs to be established
 29 to counteract the forces and couplings because of hemodynamic flow conditions.

30 In physiological flow circumstances in phosphate-buffer saline (PBS) and a platelet poor
 31 plasma (PPP) of 1 percent, the impact of physicochemical characteristics of various *S. epidermidis*
 32 strains on PE (polyethylene) adherence was investigated [117]. In the case of PBS, adhesion to all *S.*
 33 *epidermidis* strains has been evaluated by shearing up to 0 to 15 dyne/cm². Strains with greater surface

1 hydrophobicity demonstrated increased adherence to PE, showing the effect on unspecific adhesion of
2 the bacterial surface hydrophobicity. Hydrophobic adherence at mild shear pressures (0-8 dyne/cm²)
3 was well associated with bacterial adhesion. Non-specific interactions appear to regulate the adherence
4 of *S. epidermidis* directly to implants. Indeed, when plasma or serum proteins are added in the media,
5 bacterial adhesion on hydrophobic implants is significantly reduced by an order of magnitude. This
6 result reflects an increase in material surface energy after non-specific protein adsorption. Bacterial
7 biofilms are therefore not easy to remove and result frequently in chronic and recurring infections that
8 may interfere with the performance of the biomaterial, prevent healing and serve for systemic
9 infections [117].

11 **5. Summary of Device Failures due to biofilm infections**

12 Implant material and its surface type are more susceptible to adhesion of bacteria or other
13 microorganisms. Surface forces and bacterial adhesion can affect resistant biofilm-forming bacteria
14 which can lead to rejection of implant devices from the human body. To evaluate implant specificity
15 and physiological microenvironmental constraints such as microbial challenges associated with
16 orthopedic, dental and soft-tissue catheter applications discussed below with specific and objective uses of
17 NTPs in these three medical device domains:

19 **5.1. Orthopedic implants:**

20 Orthopedic implants, including total joint replacements, spinal instrumentation, and fracture fixation
21 plates, are robust structures typically crafted from durable metallic alloys (such as Ti6Al4V, CoCrMo,
22 316L stainless steel) or advanced polymers like polyether etherketone (PEEK). These implants operate
23 within an enclosed, sterile microenvironment enduring significant cyclic mechanical strain. A
24 fundamental necessity for these implants is the successful integration with bone tissue. NTP is
25 frequently employed to modify surfaces by enhancing surface energy and wettability of materials like
26 PEEK, which naturally repel water. This adjustment expedites the swift attachment and proliferation
27 of bone-forming cells (osteoblasts) and subsequent calcium phosphate deposition. In scenarios of
28 infection, such as Periprosthetic Joint Infections (PJI), the consequences can be severe, often
29 necessitating multiple surgical procedures. The common pathogens associated with PJIs are *S. aureus*
30 or *C.N. Staphylococci* [118]. NTP has hurdles of penetrating deep, inaccessible recesses at the bone-
31 implant interface to eradicate mature biofilms without inducing metallosis via surface corrosion or
32 compromising the mechanical integrity of the implant.

1 **5.2. Dental implants:**

2 These are composed of materials like titanium or zirconia, are exposed to the oral microbiome
3 (transmucosal) and undergo fluctuations in pH, temperature, and chemical exposure (dietary reactions
4 with sugars, fluorides). Dental implants are made up of commercially fabricated pure titanium or
5 zirconia, which are proven for their enhanced osseointegration and threaded structure providing a
6 gingival seal to the transmucosal abutment. Perimplantitis face challenges due to disbiotic biofilms from
7 *St. mutans* and *Po. gingivalis*. These implants necessitate surfaces that promote bone integration on
8 one end while forming a tight seal to prevent bacterial ingress on the other. Technologies such as NTPs
9 hold potential in disinfecting infected sites without compromising the implant surface. NTPs can
10 diffuse into the micro gap between the implant and the prosthesis, eradicate bacteria while
11 preserving the surface architecture for enhanced osseointegration.

13 **5.3. Intravascular catheters and soft tissue devices:**

14 Intravascular catheters, urinary catheters, and similar soft-tissue devices serve diverse functions and
15 are fashioned from pliable, low-modulus polymers such as silicone, polyurethane, or
16 polytetrafluoroethylene. These devices are designed with surfaces that deter blood clotting and
17 bacterial adhesion. Plasma treatments are commonly utilized to adjust these surfaces to reduce
18 susceptibility to fouling and biofilm formation. Catheters are vulnerable to infections caused by
19 pathogens like *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. pneumoniae*. Due to the sensitivity of polymeric devices
20 to heat and chemicals, low-temperature plasma treatments are an optimal choice for their modification.
21 The intricate construction of flow catheters presents challenges in fluid dynamics and plasma
22 physics, making techniques like NTP advantageous as cleansing agents in this domain. To
23 summarize other important studies, we have identified the type of implant materials matching the types
24 of bacteria which can become resistant with other classifications, as shown below in [Table 3](#).

25
26 **Table 3:** Table summarizing body site implants with source of microbes infecting it to prerequisite
27 diseases.

Anatomy site	Implant or Device	Implant or Device use/function	Implant or Device material	Source of microbes	Biofilm producing microbes	Biofilm incidence with (%)	Disease	Resistant?	Reference
Intravascular	Peripheral catheters (venous, arterial)	vascular access	PU, PVC, teflon	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>aeruginosa</i> , <i>C. sakazakii</i>	early-onset (acute) (2-3%)	-	YES	[119]
	Midline catheters	for patients who need I.V. therapy for more than 5 but fewer than 28 days	PU, PVC, teflon	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>aeruginosa</i> , <i>C. sakazakii</i>	early-onset (acute) to delayed (0.1%)	-	YES	[120]
	Central venous catheters non-tunnelled catheters (Cook, Arrow) tunnelled catheters (Hickman, Broviac, Groshong)	to give fluids, blood, or medications or to do medical tests quickly	Silicone, polyurethane, polyethylene	endogenous and exogenous	<i>C.N.</i> <i>Staphylococci</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Eb. species</i> , <i>C. sakazakii</i> , <i>K. pneumonia</i>	early-onset (acute) to delayed (2.5-4%)	-	YES	[121]
	Totally implanted ports (Port-a-Cath, MediPort, Infusaport)	chemotherapy, transfusion, parenteral nutrition and blood sampling, laboratory testing	PU, PVC, teflon	endogenous and exogenous	<i>C.N.</i> <i>Staphylococci</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Eb. species</i> , <i>C. sakazakii</i> , <i>K. pneumonia</i>	early-onset and delayed (2-8%)	Cancer, malnutrition	YES	[122]

Cardiovascular	Coronary stents	holds open the narrowed arteries to allow adequate blood to flow to the heart and used to treat the aorta if it has an aneurysm	Cobalt-chromium, titanium alloy, magnesium alloy	endogenous and exogenous	<i>C. sakazakii</i> , <i>C.N.</i> , <i>Staphylococci</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	early-onset acute infection (0.1%)	heart disease	NO	[123]
	Implantable defibrillators and related devices	resets the heart rhythm to prevent sudden cardiac arrest and promotes a normal heartbeat	Titanium alloy, polyurethane, silicone	endogenous and exogenous	<i>C. sakazakii</i> , <i>C.N.</i> , <i>Staphylococci</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (0.1-20%)	heart disease	NO	[124]
	Implantable patient monitors	to detect arrhythmias	Titanium alloy, polyurethane, silicone	endogenous and exogenous	<i>C. sakazakii</i> , <i>C.N.</i> , <i>Staphylococci</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (5-20%)	heart disease	NO	[125]
	Ventricular assist devices	helps pump blood from the lower chambers of your heart (the ventricles) to the rest of your body	Titanium alloy, ceramic, polyurethane	endogenous and exogenous	<i>C. sakazakii</i> , <i>C.N.</i> , <i>Staphylococci</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (16-36%)	heart disease	YES	[126]
	Mechanical heart valves	to last a patient's lifetime without the need for another valve operation because the previous valve has worn out	Titanium alloys, graphite, polyester, pyrolytic carbon,	endogenous and exogenous	<i>C.N.</i> , <i>Staphylococci</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>Eb. species</i> , <i>St. species</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (07-15%)	heart disease	YES	[127]

			cobalt-chromium						
	Vascular grafts	treatment for the long-term revascularization of occluded vessels is surgery utilizing vascular grafts, such as coronary artery bypass grafting and peripheral artery bypass grafting	Polytetrafluoroethylene, polyethylene terephthalate	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>epidermidis</i> , <i>aeruginosa</i> , <i>Eb. spec</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (1-6%)	heart disease	YES	[128]
Neurosurgical	Intracranial pressure devices	it senses the pressure inside the skull and sends measurements to a recording device	Silicone, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene	endogenous and exogenous	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. microti</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	early-onset (acute) (7-8%)	accident, trauma	YES	[129]
	Ventricular shunts	it relieves pressure on the brain caused by fluid accumulation	Silicone	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (2-27%)	accident, trauma	YES	[130]
	Ommaya reservoirs	designed to deliver medication to your cerebrospinal fluid	Silicone, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i>	early-onset (acute) (6.6%)	brain tumors, leukemia/lymphoma or leptomenigeal disease	NO	[131]
	Implantable neurological stimulators	activate or inhibit the nervous system to augment, improve, or replace	pure platinum, tungsten, platinum-	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i>	early-onset to delayed (3.11%)	neurological disease or disorder	NO	[132]

		function lost to a neurological disease or disorder	iridium alloy, or stainless steel (coated with an insulator material)						
	Spinal implants	use during surgery to treat deformity, stabilize and strengthen the spine, and facilitate fusion	Stainless steel, cobalt-chromium alloys, polyethylene, titanium	endogenous and exogenous	<i>St. species</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>C.N. staphylococci</i> , <i>Eb. species</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (0.7-20%)	accident, trauma	NO	[133]
Orthopaedic	Joint prostheses and other reconstructive orthopaedic implants	to replace a joint, bone, or cartilage due to damage or deformity, such as from breaking a leg, losing a limb, or a congenital defect	stainless steel, cobalt-chromium alloys, polyethylene, titanium alloy, ceramics	endogenous and exogenous	<i>St. species</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>C.N. staphylococci</i> , <i>Eb. species</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (0.5-4%)	accident, trauma, corrections	YES	[134]
	Fracture-fixation devices	to immobilize bone with devices such as: wires, screws, plates,	Stainless steel, cobalt-chromium	endogenous and exogenous	<i>St. species</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>C.N. staphylococci</i> ,	early-onset (acute) (5.4%)	accident, trauma	YES	[135]

		and intermedullary nails	alloys, polyethylene, titanium alloy, ceramics		<i>Po. species</i> <i>C. sakazakii.</i>				
Dental	Dental implants	used to fill in the gap left by a missing tooth or teeth	Titanium, cobalt-chromium alloy, alumina, zirconia, bioglass	endogenous and exogenous	<i>St. s species,</i> <i>A. species,</i> <i>P. species,</i> <i>P. species</i>	earringtonet, delayed, and late stage (1.4-10.6%)	accident, trauma, corrections	YES	[136]
Gynaecological	Breast implants	done for reconstructive purposes, such as after mastectomy for breast cancer, or for cosmetic reasons	Silicone	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus,</i> <i>C.N. Staphylococci,</i> <i>St. species,</i> <i>Po. species</i>	early-onset, delayed, and late stage (1-2.5%)	corrections	YES	[137]
Ophthalmological	Intra-ocular lenses	for correcting larger errors in near-sighted, far-sighted, and astigmatic eyes	Polymethylmethacrylate, silicone, acrylic	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	acute, external infection (0.08-0.36%)	corrections	YES	[138]
	Glaucoma tubes	drainage device that is implanted in the eye to divert aqueous humor (the fluid inside the eye) from the inside of the eye to an external reservoir	Polymethylmethacrylate, silicone, acrylic	endogenous and exogenous	<i>P. aeruginosa, S. microti, S. aureus</i>	acute, external infection (0.16-1.7%)	drainage of excess fluid	YES	[139]

Urological	Inflatable penile implants	intended for the treatment of erectile dysfunction, Peyronie's disease, ischemic priapism, deformity and traumatic injury of the penis, and for phalloplasty in men or phalloplasty and metoidioplasty in female-to-male gender reassignment surgery	Silicone	endogenous and exogenous	<i>C. staphylococci</i> , <i>S. species</i> , <i>Eb. species</i> , <i>A. species</i>	early-onset to delayed (2%)	erectile dysfunction, Peyronie's disease, ischemic priapism, deformity and traumatic injury and gender reassignment surgery	YES	[140]
Otolaryngological	Middle ear implants	to treat earmould allergies, skin problems in their ears, outer ear infections, narrow collapsed or closed ear canals, or malformed ears	Titanium, platinum, silicone, polytetrafluoroethylene	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>H. influenzae</i> , <i>St. species</i>	Early-onset (0.1%)	allergies, skin problems in their ears, outer ear infections, narrow, collapsed or closed ear canals, or malformed ears	NO	[141]
	Cochlear implants	to restore hearing in people with severe hearing loss who are no longer helped by using hearing aids	Titanium, platinum, silicone, polytetrafluoroethylene	endogenous and exogenous	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>H. influenzae</i> , <i>St. species</i>	early-onset (3%)	hearing loss	NO	[142]

6. Elaboration on translational and clinical considerations

6.1 Impact of material ageing and hydrophobic recovery

After undergoing NTP treatment to improve biocompatibility, titanium or polymeric implants shift to a highly energized, superhydrophilic state, facilitating initial protein adsorption and host cell attachment. Nevertheless, this state is not stable from a thermodynamic standpoint. Plasma-treated titanium experiences swift "hydrophobic recovery" within a timeframe of 5 to 7 days when kept in normal air conditions. This ageing process occurs due to the rapid decline of surface hydroxyl (–OH) groups and the inevitable absorption of airborne hydrocarbons onto the high-energy surface. The pace of this deterioration is notably influenced by the temperature during the initial plasma treatment. Treatments conducted at elevated temperatures (e.g., 200°C) produce denser, more crystalline layers that preserve their porosity longer compared to treatments at lower temperatures (e.g., 40°C)^[14]. This ageing phenomenon necessitates that on-site plasma activation at manufacturing facilities poses logistical hurdles for clinical supply chains unless the implants are preserved in specialized vacuum packaging or protective liquid surroundings. Consequently, this thermodynamic reality strongly underscores the necessity for the creation and regulatory endorsement of chair-side, point-of-care plasma devices capable of activating implants immediately before surgical implantation.

6.2 Examination of surface damage, corrosion, and galvanic effects

Biomedical implants, particularly metallic alloys like Ti6Al4V, 316L stainless steel, and CoCrMo, rely on the integrity of a delicate, naturally formed passivation layer (e.g., TiO₂ or Cr₂O₃) for their corrosion resistance in the demanding physiological milieu.

Although specific controlled plasma treatments (e.g., nitrogen PIII) can enhance corrosion resistance by forming sturdy protective layers of titanium nitride (TiN) or diamond-like carbon, aggressive direct NTP exposure or prolonged contact with highly acidic, ROS-rich plasma-activated water can jeopardize these surfaces. In environments mimicking severe inflammation, marked by high local concentrations and low pH—316L stainless steel becomes highly prone to localized pitting corrosion, while Ti6Al4V may display varying levels of passivation deterioration based on exposure duration.

Furthermore, in modular orthopedic implants (e.g., the Morse taper junctions of hip or knee arthroplasties), localized acidification of fluids prompted by plasma treatment could inadvertently worsen mechanically induced crevice corrosion or fretting corrosion. The leakage of harmful cobalt, chromium, or nickel ions due to plasma-triggered corrosion can instigate severe adverse immune responses in hosts, including the development of aseptic

1 lymphocyte-dominated vasculitis-associated lesions (ALVAL) and soft-tissue
2 pseudotumors^[144].

3 4 **6.3 Assessing host-tissue compatibility and safety limits**

5 The clinical utilization of direct NTP *in-vivo* is strictly bound by the thresholds of host-tissue
6 tolerance. To avert thermal harm, tissue coagulation, or electroporation of healthy host cells,
7 direct plasma sources must be designed to uphold effluent gas temperatures below 40°C and
8 restrict patient leakage currents to closely monitored limits (e.g., below 100 μA-rms in AC
9 mode or 10 μA in DC operation). Additionally, the generation of toxic gaseous byproducts
10 (such as excess ozone or nitrogen oxides) and the emission of UV radiation must be rigorously
11 regulated to prevent surpassing maximum daily exposure thresholds (e.g., 100 mJ/cm² for UV)
12 and prevent inducing DNA mutations in nearby healthy tissues^[145].

13 14 **6.4 Delving into penetration of established biofilms and the risk of recolonization**

15 Standard NTP treatments commonly encounter challenges in eradicating bacteria residing in
16 the deepest, oxygen-depleted layers of mature biofilms due to the rapid extinction of short-
17 lived RONS by the dense outer EPS matrix^[146]. Moreover, the formidable issue of re-
18 colonization demands attention to be addressed.

19 20 **7. Overview of Present Infection Controlling Strategies**

21 **7.1 Physical approaches**

22 The removal of medical devices and debridement and debridement continued are the best treatment
23 alternatives to eradicate biofilms when standardized therapy fails to successfully remove
24 biofilm infections associated with medical devices^[147]. The removal of biofilm-infected
25 implants such as prosthetic joints and pacemakers, cannot be the optimum solution due to
26 technical challenges and significant morbidity. An efficient physical approach for eliminating
27 biofilms is photodynamic therapy (PDT). It consists of three major components: light
28 photosensitizer, a chemical compound, and oxygen^[148,149]. Light has an antimicrobial action
29 at a certain wavelength. Antibacterial PDT creates high-cytotoxic ROS or excitable singlet
30 oxygen, causing damage to cells, cellular membranes and organelle breakdown and even cell
31 death, to the biological components on or in cell membranes such as proteins, nucleic acids and
32 lipids. A recent study found that *E. Faecalis* biofilms formed on root channels can not only be
33 inhibited by PDT, but also can be prevented from forming ROS in biofilm infections, by
34 inhibiting expression of toxic factors that affect early bacterial adhesion and by promoting the

1 formation of the structure of biofilms matrix ^[150]. In order to increase the PDT's impact,
2 nanoparticles can also be utilized in PDT, either by producing heat or by converting
3 nanomaterials into species which kill biofilms ^[151]. PDT is mostly utilized for dental plaque-
4 related illness therapy ^[152]. Other implant-related biofilm infections, such as prosthetic joint
5 infections and ventilator-associated pulmonary biofilm infections, might be controlled via PDT
6 technology ^[153]. Although preclinical research has shown that PDT is an excellent method for
7 the treatment of biofilm infections, many actions remain to be done before clinical practice can
8 be implemented safely as shown in [Figure 4](#). PDT's short-term adverse effects are typically
9 moderate and limited, such as erythema, edema and skin discomfort, but long-term light
10 exposure may lead to cataracts, skin carcinoma and other adverse consequences ^[154]. Protective
11 precautions should be performed during PDT to protect the eyes of patients from laser exposure
12 and not to harm the surrounding tissue of a patient by photosensitizers and photochemical
13 reactions ^[155].

14 Studies have demonstrated that ultrasound-targeted microbubble destruction (UTMD)
15 can improve antibacterial active ingredients, resulting in strong biofilm clearance effect ^[156].
16 In addition, UTMD may degrade the matrix structure of bacterial biofilms with the help of
17 cavitation to encourage drug entry into the biofilm, and can directly kill cells and boost
18 metabolic activity of cells to increase antibiotic bactericidal ability ^[157]. These findings give
19 new insights for the use of ultrasound and UTMD in improving antibiotic treatment efficacy in
20 biofilms associated to prosthesis or catheter and these methods have demonstrated potential *in-*
21 *vivo* effects ^[158]. However, bacterial activity in biofilms is influenced by a range of variables
22 including the acoustic intensity, pulse cycle, frequency and duration of ultrasound-mediated
23 antibiotic action ^[159]. A greater intensity of ultrasound and longer duration can harm the skin
24 tissue, or cause germs to propagate and influence blood flow to the surrounding tissue.
25 Implant damage might also be caused by cavitation ^[160]. Since this approach may be utilized
26 in future clinical practice, additional study is required in order to choose the optimum
27 ultrasound settings.

Figure 4: Representation of current infection controlling strategies for the elimination from biofilm infected implants. It covers photodynamic therapy, nanoparticles-enabled photodynamic therapy, deuterium photodynamic therapy, use of antimicrobial coating, metal composites and antiadhesive coatings for biofilm (Created using Biorender.com).

The use of water jets is an efficient physical approach by means of mechanical pulse and pressures to remove biofilms on the surface of implants [161]. Water jets might wash off plaques that are weakly adhered, remove bacterial cells that interfere with the development of biofilms [162]. An earlier study has demonstrated that the effectiveness of dental water jets to eliminate biofilms is variable under different pressure settings. Research shows that the biofilm diminution rate was 85% and 63.4%, at pressures of 350 and 102 kPa, respectively [163]. A recent study showed that PDT and water jets together have high potential to remove the biofilm from the surface of conventional implants. Compared to untreated biofilm, the impact or force of a water jet facilitated the removal of *Streptococcus mutans* formed on a titanium surface treated with PDT [164]. This has shown that PDT can weaken biofilm at various phases, facilitating the separation with a simple washing force [165]. In a further investigation, a cavitating jet may clear up biofilms generated on the rough surface of implant screws,

1 particularly on the root, efficiently (as shown in the graphical abstract) ^[166]. Moreover the use
2 of a dental biofilm and hygiene surrounding the implant may be efficiently cleansed by
3 mechanical techniques such as the use of a plastic curette, a perio-flow device, a Ti brush,
4 implantoplasty and electrochemical treatments ^[167]. Dissolution of implant material is therefore
5 a significant factor in treating peri-implant inflammation in the clinical choice ^[168].

7.2 Surface Modification

8 The use of anti-bacterial coatings or anti-adhesive chemicals may effectively block
9 microorganism adhesion and prevent biofilm formation, which is an essential strategy to battle
10 biofilm in the use of medical products. Antibacterial coating methods avoid biofilm formation
11 and growth through bacteriostatic or bactericidal effects on medical equipment. The efficacy
12 of preventing catheter-related and other implant-related infections ^[169] has widely
13 demonstrated in traditional antibacterial coatings like chlorhexidine, gentamicin,
14 minocycline, rifampicin, silver sulfadiazine, mupirocin and vancomycin. Multiple
15 antimicrobials, such as the use of minocycline and rifampicin antibiotics in combination, have
16 demonstrated good benefits in avoiding drug resistance ^[170]. The widespread usage of
17 antimicrobial coating, on the other hand, might contribute to bacterial antibiotic resistance. So
18 far, antibacterial coating research has concentrated on the creation of new antibacterial
19 chemical coatings or on mimicking natural defense functions to avoid biofilm formation ^[171–173].
20 The surfaces of the medical device materials are modified to prevent biofilm development by
21 killing bacteria or reducing bacterial adherence by use of antifouling compound layering or
22 anti-adhesive layer. The development of biofilms on the stainless steel and polyethylene
23 surface has been proved to inhibit isoeugenol coating due to its good antibacterial activity ^[174].
24 N-acetylcysteine is an authorized medicinal product by the Food and Drug Administration
25 (FDA) which is extensively utilized in various conditions, including chronic bronchitis, heart
26 deflection, and paracetamol toxicity ^[175].

27 The medication is indicated to inhibit bacterial adhesion and to prevent the formation
28 of biofilms, and not just antibacterial action. The medication is indicated to inhibit bacterial
29 adhesion and to prevent the formation of biofilms, and not just antibacterial action ^[176]. Existing
30 biomaterials and other reagent coating techniques create long term degradation-suitable
31 surfaces. The history of metal-based compounds as antibacterial agents, for example, silver
32 coatings used on various medical equipment, is extensive since it was utilized ^[177]. Enhanced
33 antibacterial activity and decreased cytotoxicity are presented by nanomaterials (NMs) ^[178]. In
34 order to avoid attaching microbes to medical devices, silver nanoparticle (AgNP) coatings are

1 also used. Recent studies have revealed topographical effects on the adhesion pattern and
2 degree of expansion of the bacterial cell membrane on nanostructure surfaces ^[179]. The medical
3 devices also employ new metals and metal-ceramic composites. For example, a copper-bearing
4 titanium alloy has been shown to efficiently kill the bacteria attached by damaging cell
5 membranes and cell walls and strongly inhibit the formation of biofilm and prevent bacterial
6 infection by dental implants which is highly potential to be used in dental implants with
7 excellent antibacterial viability and an excellent bone reactivation effect ^[180].

8 A study performed by Dao et.al., demonstrated that radical-rich, oxygen-assisted plasma
9 polymerized (IPP) antimicrobial (CSA-90) coatings on SS used in a murine model of
10 orthopedic infection (Figure 5A). This work showed enhanced antibacterial activity against *S.*
11 *aureus* and osseointegration ^[181]. The IPP deposition retained intact even after incubation in
12 Tyrode's Simulated Body Fluid (SBF) at 37°C to exhibit that CSA90-IPP coatings can
13 withstand complex surgical site infections post-surgery (Figure 5 B-D). This work also
14 satisfactorily showed that the initial density of radicals embedded in the IPP to the crosslinking
15 degree associated with covalent bonding on the SS-pins can regulate oxidation kinetics. A
16 preclinical murine orthopedic infection model exhibited where a localized bone defect was
17 made in the proximal tibia and SS-pins inserted in the medullary space as a nidus for
18 biofilm formation and infection (Figure 5 E & F). This was assessed by comparing three groups
19 as shown in the studies 1. Control group (SS-pins without plasma treatment and CSA90), 2.
20 IPP SS-pins and 3. IPP CSA90 coated SS-pins. Radiography (Figure 5 G-I) for group 3, showed
21 lower bacterial load against *S. aureus* and higher bone regeneration volume. Micro-CT (Figure
22 5J & K) histology (Figure 5 L-O) analyses for all the three groups showed almost similar bone
23 regeneration at specific sites of the SS-pins placements.

1
2 Figure 5: A) Schematic illustration of a two-step process consisting of ion-assisted plasma
3 polymerization (PP) to form radical-rich coatings on 3D materials followed by CSA-90
4 covalent functionalization. The antibacterial efficacy of the coatings to reduce *S. aureus*
5 infection-related bone loss was evaluated in a murine model of orthopedic infection. Semi-
6 quantitative analysis of relative bacterial load (absorbance at 600 nm) from B) bone swabs, C)
7 intramedullary steel pins, and D) soft tissue adjacent to the defect site. N = 10 per group with
8 Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc multiple comparisons (Mann-Whitney U). Error bars show
9 mean and SEM; (* p-value ≤ 0.05 ; ** p-value ≤ 0.01). E) The bacterial loads (absorbance at
10 600 nm) recovered from the silicon beads with *S. aureus* (1×10^4 CFU) inoculated and air
11 dried. F) The bacterial loads (absorbance at 600 nm) recovered from stainless-steel pins (1 cm

1 in length) with *S. aureus* (1×10^5 CFU) inoculated on the surface. (N = 3 per group; Error bars:
2 mean and SEM; Statistical analysis was completed using 2way ANOVA and Turkey's Test and
3 unpaired t-test; (** p-value ≤ 0.01 ; *** p-value ≤ 0.001). Radiographs (X-ray images) G-I)
4 showing osteolytic bone loss in infected tibiae with G) uncoated pins and bone healing in select
5 tibiae from groups with H) PP coated pins and I) PP + CSA-90 coated pins. Radiographs show
6 images before (left) and after (right) pin removal. The white arrows point to the osteolytic
7 lesions of the tibial drilled hole due to infections. Scale bar = 6 mm. J) Micro-CT
8 reconstructions. Scale bar = 1 mm. K) Micro-CT data showing bone volume (mm³) in the tibial
9 drilled hole; N = 10 per group with Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc multiple comparisons
10 (Mann-Whitney U). There was significantly improved defect repair in the PP + CSA-90 group
11 ($p < 0.05^*$). BV was increased in the PP group, but this did not reach statistical significance
12 ($p = 0.319$, no coating versus PP; and $p = 0.4313$, PP vs PP + CSA-90). The white arrows point
13 to the non-union osteolytic lesions of the tibial drilled hole. H&E-stained sections illustrating
14 the healing of the bone defects in L, M) no coating, N) PP-coated and O) PP + CSA-90 groups.
15 Scale bars equal to 600 μm (L, N, O) and 200 μm (M). (Black arrows: woven cortical bones;
16 yellow arrows: inflammatory macrophages and lymphocytes) [176]. Copyright 2024. Adapted
17 from John Wiley & Sons.

18
19 Micro arc oxidation treatment of titanium has enhanced surface roughness,
20 hydrophilicity, corrosion resistance and has excellent antibacterial activities against the *S.*
21 *aureus*, which makes it highly applicable as a hard tissue implant [182]. *S. mutans* biofilm
22 development forms the same as polymer-infiltrated Polycrystalline zirconium dioxide
23 ceramic which can inhibit the formation of biofilms and have high biocompatibility with human
24 osteoblasts [183]. Antiadhesion coatings are also produced in order for the bacteria not to attach
25 readily anymore by altering the physical and chemical properties of surfaces. In order to inhibit
26 the growth of *S. epidermidis* biofilm on polystyrene surfaces, hydrophobin is utilized to coat
27 different physically important materials and has been proven to be efficient [184]. High surface
28 roughness, hydrophobicity and surface-free energy contribute towards early adherence of
29 microorganisms. The properties of the resin surface are changed by cyanoacrylate adhesives,
30 surface roughness decreases, hydrophilicity increases, and surface free energy increases
31 therefore inhibiting biofilm development [185]. Ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene
32 (UHMWPE) is the most prevalent polymer used in total knee and hip arthroplasty. UHMWPE
33 is a type of solid, inert and stable polymer. However, it is also sensitive to adhesion and the
34 development of biofilms due to its high hydrophobic surface. Polymer hydrophilic layers, such

1 as chemical covalent bonds that alter the chemistry of surface from hydrophobic to hydrophilic
2 and inhibit bacterial adherence and biofilm development, which are grafted on the UHMWPE
3 surface of a polymer coating ^[186].

4 Large research on biofilm formation prevention has been carried out to identify suitable
5 materials to be implanted in the human body and operate better through changes in the surface
6 characteristics of such materials as roughness, hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity, surface free
7 energy, and electric charge. For example, in addition to the effective resistance to bacterial
8 adhesion, the modification of the surface of orthopaedic implants should also be considered
9 and evaluated for the functional retention of raw material implants, biocompatibility, resistance
10 of tribological corrosion of the cover and host cell non-toxicity ^[187]. *S. aureus* is one of the
11 most prominent bio-film medical device microbes and offers a significant medical problem
12 because of its high incidence and resistance to medicines. *S. aureus* surface proteins can attach
13 to extracellular proteins such as fibrins, fibronectins, and collagen in particular, the virulence
14 factor. These proteins are found to have affinity towards implant and quickly adheres to the
15 surface of the implant. Thus the *S. aureus* adhesion to the implant surface is mediated by these
16 proteins ^[191]. Such mediating proteins present a feasible way of avoiding *S. aureus* biofilm
17 development on implant surfaces by targeting them to decrease or block their synthesis, or
18 diminish their adsorption ability. Biofilm development on *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* indwelling
19 medical devices (for example tissue plasminogen activator (tPA)) decreases *S. aureus*
20 formation. The tPA coating inhibits early bacterial adhesion by breaking local fibrin and the
21 subsequent buildup. Moreover, the cover of tPA enhances the susceptibility to antibiotic
22 biocidal infection. Substances adsorbed in the surface, leading to adsorption of intermediate
23 protein on the coating surface which may reduce the bacterial adhesion to the surface and thus
24 inhibit the formation and infection caused by biofilms, are the result of monomeric trimethyl
25 silane and oxygen plasma coatings. Device-related infections produced by *S. aureus* biofilms
26 have been proven by the pathway of coagulation to trigger the synthesis of prothrombin and
27 fibrin. Direct fibrin inhibitors may be utilized to cover the bonding of biomaterial surfaces
28 and subsequent device-related infections ^[193]. Another method to prevent colonization of
29 microorganisms is by altering the structural integrity of biofilm and the development of
30 biofilms, as shown in [Figure 6](#). The immobilization of biofilm enzymes on material surfaces is
31 considered one of the best techniques to inhibit the development of biofilms. For example, a
32 deoxyribonuclease I (DNase I) coating has a strong anti-infection capability and
33 biocompatibility to improve implant success ^[192]. Polypyrrole is an organic conductive polymer
34 formed from a pyrrole circular structure that has an impact on biofilm integrity by promoting

1 a structure that includes repeated and positive load-regulating ionic transverse cross-bindings
 2 and ensuing aggregation to easily wash away biological films with water [193]. The combined
 3 use of these steps might lead to increased antibiotic activity in films. The safety of the host
 4 must be considered, regardless of the safeguards adopted and raw materials must be guaranteed
 5 to function.

6 Figure 6: Summary of antibiofilm therapeutic target sites includes cellular membrane involving
 7 MSCRAMM inhibitors, pilicides, competitive inhibitors of adhesins, monoclonal antibodies,
 8 DNase and the intracellular pathway (Created using Biorender.com).

9
 10 clinical research on the modification of the surface of medical devices, as already
 11 noted, was highly effective in order to better protect implanted medical devices from bacterial
 12 infections, but the proposed techniques and their clinical application continue to differ
 13 considerably. Because of cytotoxicity, immunosuppression or genotoxicity issues, most
 14 coatings being investigated are not appropriate for medical implantation. Some technologies
 15 have, however, proven enough that antibacterial coatings such as AgNP coatings can be offered
 16 in clinical practice for efficacy, safety and sustainability have been provided such coatings have
 17 been used in clinical practice [194]. For instance, a hydrogel-coated antimicrobial prosthesis can
 18 securely protect the prosthesis and decrease early operational site infections during medium
 19 follow-up to 2 years without negative effects [195]. A further investigation revealed that silver-
 20 coated mega prostheses with 2.2% local argyria with no systemic side effects are beneficial in
 21 reducing prosthetic joint infections [194]. The development of medical device surfaces with

1 outstanding antibacterial characteristics with high biocompatibility, and long-term antibacterial
2 efficacy is yet a breakthrough to be utilized in better clinical practice. Other infection
3 controlling strategies include: antimicrobial peptides, NMs, degrading agents for the ECM of
4 biofilms, and bacteriophage treatment.

6 **8. Direct and indirect plasma applications in infection control**

7 The optimized working parameters of NTPs enhance direct interactions with biological
8 tissues and biomaterials, but low-pressure plasmas are, on the other hand, more suitable to
9 introduce external species to the surface of the materials before coming into contact with
10 corporal fluids and tissues, such as orthopaedic and dental implants coated in plasma. Such
11 interfaces that are triggered by the plasma may be classified into two categories: direct and
12 indirect interfaces.

14 **8.1 Direct plasma interaction with microbes/biomaterials**

15 The NTPs contain electrons, ions and other plasma species which are widely used to
16 expose them to cells, bacteria and the tissue in terms of direct interactions (such plasmas are
17 generated in atmospheric as well as in low pressures). Plasmas may be used to carry out the
18 intended tasks with NTPs for sterilization, healing of wounds, blood coagulation, and skin
19 disease and cancer treatments [196–199]. For example, an active NTP species may destroy
20 microorganisms, such as bacteria, viruses and fungus, but does not cause thermal harm to
21 normal tissues, using the atmospheric radio frequency or microwave discharge method [200,201].
22 In general, a non-thermal plasma is ionized to react with the surface components that then cause an
23 chemistry of reactive oxygen (ROS) species, such as $\cdot\text{OH}$, O_2 , and $^1\text{O}_2$, that interferes with
24 the cell's metabolic activities [197]. The high concentrations of electron and ion contribute to the
25 killing and disruption of microorganisms via physical contact as shown below in [Figure 7](#).
26 Direct interfaces operate faster and accurately and have numerous potential uses compared to
27 indirect interfaces on prepared biomaterials. Plasmas can stimulate wound healing surfaces by
28 inhibiting microorganisms and regulate dermal and epidermal cell differentiation. In the
29 treatment of atopic dermatitis and in pruritus relief, they are also beneficial in stimulating the
30 immune system [202].

1
 2 Figure 7: Proposed mechanism of action of NTPs with Gram-negative and Gram-positive
 3 bacteria. (a to c) Proposed inactivation mechanism of Gram-negative bacteria. (a) Structure of
 4 Gram-negative bacteria before treatment, in which the cell envelope consists of a thin layer of
 5 peptidoglycan and lipopolysaccharide; (b) NTP-generated ROS attacking both cell envelope
 6 and intracellular components, in which the cell envelope is the major target; (c) inactivation
 7 mainly caused by cell leakage, with some DNA damage possible. (d to f) Proposed inactivation
 8 mechanism of Gram-positive bacteria. (d) Structure of Gram-positive bacteria before
 9 treatment, in which the cell envelope consists of a thick rigid layer of peptidoglycan; (e) NTP-
 10 generated ROS attacking both cell envelope and intracellular components, in which
 11 intracellular materials are the major targets; (f) inactivation mainly caused by intracellular
 12 damage (e.g., DNA breakage) but not leakage^[203].

13
 14 To discuss NTPs antimicrobial efficacy against biofilms/bacteria we establish below
 15 inactivation mechanisms of oxidative damage and physical disruption by a multipronged NTPs
 16 action:

- 17
 18 1. Direct oxidation of macromolecules: NTP-generated RONS induce severe lipid peroxidation
 19 in the bacterial plasma membrane. This leads to a catastrophic loss of structural integrity,
 20 membrane depolarization, the formation of transient pores, and the subsequent leakage of vital
 21 intracellular contents, including DNA, ATP and essential cytosolic proteins.

- 1 2. Nucleic acid and protein cleavage: Reactive species that successfully penetrate the bacterial
2 envelope cause profound oxidative lesions to nucleic acids (e.g., the formation of 8-
3 oxoguanine) and induced both single and double strand DNA breaks.
- 4 3. EPS matrix degradation: A critical translational hurdle in biofilm management is the
5 extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) matrix, which acts as a formidable physical and
6 chemical shield against both host immune cells and exogenous antibiotics^[204].

7

8 The new area of plasma medicine, for example, is formed from plasma technology as
9 an interdisciplinary subject ^[11,198,199]. NTPs are frequently produced between electrodes in the
10 gas flow at atmospheric pressure. Previous investigations have shown that NTPs are microbial
11 effects on infection by preventing the growth of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria,
12 fungi, and viruses. NTPs have numerous benefits compared to standard antibacterial methods.
13 First, NTPs can interact with the body's surface materials, medical equipment, tumor and a
14 microbial barrier directly ^[205,206]. Secondly, more environment-friendly plasmas complement
15 autoclave methods and chemical sterilization with ethylene oxide on thermo-labile surfaces
16 ^[207]. Thirdly, mild conditions make it easier for NTP instruments to be designed and marketed
17 with attributes such as convenience, relatively inexpensive, and portability ^[208]. During the
18 process, gases such as air, O₂, N₂, He and Ar are utilized to produce plasmas including
19 electrons, ROSs, reactive nitrogen species (RNSs), ions, UV rays etc. that are important to the
20 elimination of microbiological species by radiation from the UV and ROS ^[209–212]. UV light
21 can damage the genetic material and photo-desorption etch the bacterial membrane. In addition,
22 the ROS can communicate with these organisms to cause chain reactions that interfere with the
23 metabolism and consequently there are physiological changes in the treatment of the
24 microorganisms, such as membrane damage, leakage of intracellular macromolecules, and
25 fragmentation of DNA ^[210]. Experimental processes show that plasma species and power
26 sources should be carefully chosen to create enough UV and ROS to kill bacteria.

27

28 **8.2. Indirect plasma interaction with device surfaces**

29 In biomaterial design and engineering, an efficient plasma deposition is normally
30 performed with a low-pressure plasma in pulsed AC or DC mode ^[213]. Plasma deposition is a
31 mature and widespread technology for making thick and thin coatings and for modifying a
32 wide range of surface chemical compounds and structures. In order to create high deposition
33 rates and different microstructures on substrates, the chamber can be filled with a high-density
34 plasma ^{[214,215][216]}. Surface structures with metallic or non-metallic species or a mix can be

1 developed by employing appropriate plasma components and instrumental settings to increase
2 particular qualities such as hardness, adhesiveness, friction and other chemical and biological
3 features. As a state-of-the-art plasma method, plasma ion immersion implantation and
4 deposition (PIII&D) is the flexible means of modifying and functionalizing the surface of
5 materials. It is a very efficient and versatile non-line-of-sight technique and is particularly
6 suitable for complicated samples and industrial components [217][218].

7 An external power source such as DC, RF and ECR generates gas plasma (air, oxygen,
8 nitrogen, argon etc.), whereas metal plasmas generally are created from plasma sources of
9 vacuum arc [219]. Indirect surfaces are developed on the basis of the design of sophisticated
10 materials which are available *in-vivo*. Implants with an appropriate compatibility do not
11 generally contain enough intrinsic antibacterial capability, but in many clinical applications,
12 biocompatibility and bacterial resistance are extremely desirable. For instance titanium (Ti)
13 alloys and polyether ether ketone (PEEK) have inherent poor antibacterial capability and
14 biocompatibility, however the qualities on the surface may be enhanced by changing the
15 physical and chemical features [220]. A recent study by Yan et al. on Ti implants showed
16 nonthermal atmospheric-pressure nitrogen plasma can improve the hydrophilicity of pure
17 titanium (Figure 8) without damaging its surface morphology while introducing nitrogen-
18 containing functional groups, thereby promoting cell attachment, proliferation, and
19 osseointegration (Figure 9).

Preprint

1
2 Figure 8 SEM analysis of the (A and D) Ti, (B and E) plasma-treated Ti, and (C and F) N₂-
3 Plasma treated Ti discs. Scanning probe micrographs of the (G) Ti, (H) Plasma treated Ti, and
4 (I) N₂-Plasma treated Ti discs and (J) Contact angles of the Ti, Plasma treated Ti, and N₂-
5 Plasma-treated Ti discs. * $p < 0.05$ compared with Ti. Figure 8 (G–I) shows the results of
6 scanning probe microscopy (SPM; SPM-9600; Shimadzu). The surface morphological features
7 of all samples were uniform and similar, and no significant difference in mean surface
8 roughness (Ra) among the samples could be observed [221]. Copyright 2022. Adapted from
9 MDPI.

1
2 Figure 9: Reconstructed three-dimensional microcomputed tomography transverse slices of rat
3 femurs containing (A) Ti, (B) Plasma treated Ti, and (C) N₂-Plasma treated Ti implants after 8
4 weeks (red, implants; blue, cancellous bone; gray, cortical bone). Reconstructed three-
5 dimensional micro-CT images of bone tissues around the (D) Ti, (E) Plasma-treated Ti, (F) N₂-
6 Plasma treated Ti implants (red, implants; blue, new bone). (G) Bone volume to total volume
7 ratio (BV/TV), (H) trabecular thickness (Tb. Th), (I) trabecular number (Tb. N), and (J)
8 trabecular separation (Tb. Sp) around the Ti, Plasma-treated Ti, and N₂-Plasma-treated Ti
9 implants after 8 weeks. * p < 0.05 compared with Ti; # p < 0.05 compared with Plasma treated
10 Ti [221]. Copyright 2022. Adapted from MDPI.

11

1 Silver (Ag) may be used with biomaterials to enhance antibacterial capacity, and Ag
2 seldom results in microbial resistance as a broad-range antibacterial agent. Ag is often scattered
3 in a solution as bactericidal, although generally the dosage is higher than the dangerous limit.
4 By utilizing plasma technology, Ag ions are injected into the nanoparticles of biomaterials [222].
5 By altering the plasma conditions and the Ag NPs with 5 nm have been discovered to generate
6 the greatest antibacterial rate, the size, distribution, and profound diffusion of the nanoparticles
7 may be regulated. Moreover, plasma-modified surfaces are typically biocompatible to the
8 correct quantity of Ag NPs, and normal tissues may attach and proliferate [223]. For example,
9 diamond-like coating (DLC) films that are made of plasma are highly antibacterial, low-
10 friction, atomic smooth and corrosion-resistant. For instance, DLC has strong antibacterial
11 capacities. Ag can be integrated with other interface elements for numerous functions [224]. Liu
12 et al. for example have refined Ag and Si doped polyamine 66 where Ag leads to improved
13 bone regeneration and high antibacterial effectiveness. It is also found to surface ductility and elastic
14 modulus. Less Ag ions are discharged in the first 3 weeks following the implantation compared
15 to Ag doping alone. Upregulated expression of genes of bone regeneration (iNOS and nNOS)
16 is also found [224]. Ag nanoparticles distributed in a solution or implanted in a substratum react
17 via a variety of ways with bacteria. Ag dispersed nanoparticles generally kill bacteria directly
18 as a release of Ag ion in a solution. The NPs respond simultaneously to the substratum and
19 bacteria when integrated in the substratum. The Ag ions are flushed into the solution so that
20 there are enough electrons on Ag NPs and delivered to bacteria with the influence of the ROS
21 chain it ruptures the membrane and ultimately leading to cell death. This antibiotic mediated
22 electron transfer mechanism depends on the size that Ag NPs in the 5–25 nm range are best
23 used to accumulate electrons, but on the other hand the bigger particles are harmful to normal
24 tissues and can cause severe cytosolic leakage and lysis [225]. The galvanic effect may be
25 extended to the Mg and Ag contacts. This hybrid system makes Mg release easier, but lowers
26 Ag ion leaching. This enhances the antibacterial effectiveness and osteogenic characteristics
27 while reducing cytotoxicity [226]. In conclusion, Ag nanoparticles introduced by plasma
28 technology produces multi-functional antimicrobial interfaces.

29 Zinc (Zn) may promote the osseointegration as an important trace element to support
30 physiological metabolism by increasing cell adhesion, immunological functions, activity of
31 alkaline phosphatases and skeletal development. Furthermore, Zn ion oxidation stress causes
32 antibacterial effects and Zn is frequently coated in implants to improve retention strength,
33 integration of osseogenesis and antibacterial characteristics [227]. For example, Fang et al.
34 studied Zn-incorporated Ti is generated by PIII and materials provide a living habitat for

1 osteoblasts to adhere and proliferate. Also, the Zn decorated interface reduces bacterial growth,
2 although the breakdown in the osseointegration process typically prevents Zn coatings from
3 lasting [228]. Zhao et al. created TiO₂ crystalline by impinging Zn ions on it by combining
4 plasma spraying and PIII which were discharged at a modest speed to provide extended support
5 during osseogenesis while offering bacterial resistance against *S. aureus*. While release of Zn
6 ions may be slower, unchecked release might interfere with initial homeostasis leading to the
7 absence of other trace elements such as iron and calcium [229]. Jin et al. reported Zn regulated
8 incorporation to fulfil therapeutic demands, it is also necessary that Zn implants be
9 synthesized in a controlled way. PIII&D is an interface-controlled approach that integrates the
10 desired parts by adjusting its implantation duration and the optimal process has good osteogenic
11 activity and antibacterial properties [230].

12 A study showed interactions between oxygen PIII (O-PIII) on Ti and blood where higher
13 voltage provides a rutile phase of the TiO₂ interface, resulting to trigger platelets to speed blood
14 coagulation and adhere to bacteria. Ti bone implants benefit from the positive characteristics
15 provided by O-PIII [231]. Nitrogen PIII (N-PIII) improves the polyurethane (PU) surface
16 roughness, which displays enhanced three-dimensional structure with sinuous folds and makes the
17 surface more hydrophilic, providing a resistance to durable *S. aureus* habitat [232]. In order to
18 generate synergistic effects, N-PIII is coupled with other methods. Zheng et al. have developed
19 micro-arc-oxidized and nitrogen developed TiO₂ coatings on the Ti surface. The incorporation of
20 nitrogen increases photocatalysis by changing from UV to visible light the absorbent area,
21 allowing N-TiO₂ as an interface to use visible light for the destruction of bacteria [233]. The
22 combination of Ag and N-PIII on the interface with good surface roughness, hydrophilicity,
23 protein adhesion, cytocompatibility and bacterial resistance, whereas excessive of Ag NPs
24 presents harm to normal cells [234]. O-PIII and N-PIII were also used in tandem in creating
25 functional groups such as C=NH, C-NH₂ and C=O on the surface of poly(Butylene succinate),
26 therefore increasing the antibacterial capacity [235].

27 Functionalities depend on the elemental distributions on the coating. If oxygen and the
28 substratum have more affinity than metal and oxygen, an oxide layer can be built with the
29 doped-up metallic species. Polak et al. employed H₂O-PIII to generate the oxide layer at Ti
30 surface and the use of H₂O in comparison with PIII inhibits water-insoluble copper oxide
31 production or the profound absorption into titanium oxide of copper atoms. The O₂-Cu PIII
32 sample therefore includes profound oxide at the surface of titanium oxide copper, whereas
33 the H₂O-Cu PIII sample concurrently creates metallic copper in titanium oxide. The hybrid
34 interface is highly biocompatible, derived from oxidized titanium and regulated copper ion

1 release [231]. A study by Los et al. carried out deposition of antibiotics - ampicillin and
2 gentamicin on 96-well microliter plates and steel coupons surface using an atmospheric plasma
3 system by TheraDep. The deposited materials were challenged against both planktonic and
4 sessile *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* and were observed for 14 days. The preservation of
5 antimicrobial action and effectiveness of antibiotic-coated surfaces against *E. coli* and *P.*
6 *aeruginosa* was observed [236].

7 A novel study by Akhavan et.al., approached to fabricate antimicrobial coatings on
8 titanium implant surfaces using ion-rich plasma polymerization (IPP) that effectively inhibited
9 the growth of both fungal (*C. albicans*) and bacterial (*S. aureus*) pathogens [237]. This work
10 involved A two-step process involving ion-assisted plasma polymerization and covalent
11 immobilization of antimicrobial peptides (Mel4 and caspofungin) on the coating as shown in
12 [Figure 10 A](#) [237]. The plasma polymerized coating exhibited high mechanical stability and
13 retained a reservoir of long-lived radicals, enabling covalent binding of the peptides. ToF-
14 SIMS analysis confirmed the covalent attachment of the peptides, which remained even after
15 rigorous washing (not shown here). The Mel4-coated surfaces effectively inhibited the
16 adhesion and proliferation of *S. aureus* compared to uncoated titanium ([Figure 10 B](#)) [237]. The
17 caspofungin-coated surfaces showed a significant reduction (>log 4) in *C. albicans* adhesion
18 and biofilm formation, even after 6 months of storage ([Figure 10 C-E](#)) [237]. The combination
19 of mechanical stability, antimicrobial efficacy, and ease of fabrication makes this approach
20 promising for developing anti-infective implantable devices. This work is exemplary due to its
21 foreseen direct application that can be made to dental implants which has 50% or more
22 incidence of peri-implantitis, a disease caused by eukaryotic and prokaryotic pathogens as
23 tested here. Such work with plasma also opens the domain in co-immobilization of multiple
24 antimicrobial peptides as well as bone cell signaling biomolecules to aid in the development of
25 such superior osteogenic dental implant surfaces [237].

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 2 Figure 10: (A) Schematic illustration of the two-step process for the development of coatings
 3 that prevent colonization by *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*. Step 1 involves ion-assisted deposition
 4 of a plasma-polymerized layer with embedded long-lived radicals onto titanium substrates. Step
 5 2 involves overnight incubation of the PP-coated titanium surfaces in the antimicrobial
 6 solution, where the peptide covalently binds to the PP layer on contact. B) Image analysis of
 7 the percentage of surfaces covered by *S. aureus*, after 18 h of incubation. The samples were
 8 stained using a live/dead fluorescent stain. Scale bar equals 200 μm . C) Growth of *C.*
 9 *albicans* on coated surfaces Ti, Ti-pp and Ti-Caspo after 24 h incubation. Expressed in number
 10 of viable fungal colonies per area (cm^2). The test threshold is capped at 50 CFU/cm^2 , the
 11 minimum detectable limit of this assay. D) Growth of *C. albicans* on coated surfaces after 3
 12 months of storage under ambient conditions. (E) Representative images showing *C.*

1 *albicans* growth after 4 and 24 h of incubation, by fluorescent microscopy
2 (green = live/red = dead), 10× magnification. The assay verified background (VB) is indicated
3 by dotted lines. Scale bar equals to 200 μm [237]. Copyright 2018. Reproduced with permission
4 from Elsevier.

5

6 In addition, Plasma activation of liquids (PAL) represent a purely indirect therapeutic
7 modality where the plasma discharge occurs over or within a liquid medium. These liquids
8 include: water, saline and cell growth medium. PAL treatment also lead to substantial
9 inactivation of microbes [238]. Water treated by plasma discharges regularly shown strong
10 bactericidal action, which was supposed to be caused by the existence of stabilized reactive
11 nitrogen and oxygen types [239]. PALs produce relatively long-lived RONS (e.g., H₂O₂, NO₂⁻,
12 NO₃⁻) in the aqueous medium thereby changing properties such as pH, conductivity, ORP,
13 TDS, D.O. The most responsible agents are in particular ·OH radical, ozone, atomic oxygen
14 and hydrogen peroxide. In the RNS, nitric oxide, nitrites and peroxynitrite species are present
15 [240]. The combination impact of hydrogen peroxide added to nitrite rather than oxidation by
16 the former two alone, appears to be a result of enhanced antimicrobial activity [241].
17 Interestingly, the combined actions of these oxidizing agents and an acidic pH appear to be the
18 resultant antimicrobial effects of PALs in that a low pH produces ideal circumstances for the
19 cell membrane's penetration by the ROS. Acidic circumstances, particularly those generated
20 by hydroperoxyl radicals that possess significant oxidation capabilities and induce membrane
21 fatty acid peroxidation can also expedite chemical processes. Due to the same chemical
22 mechanism, the plasma-activated liquid lipid peroxidation and then cross-link reaction from
23 the fatty acid side chain are affected by the damage caused directly by the leaking of
24 intracellular DNA and proteins [242]. Significantly, O and ·OH radicals in the membrane
25 generate temporary pores that ultimately result in depolarization and permeabilization.
26 However, effectiveness must be standardized by control of the reactive species contained in
27 the fluid in order to use PAL as antibacterial treatment. The major technique to regulate the
28 composition of the reactive species has been the use of various plasma working gases. The
29 plasma jet design is based on one plasma source extensively used for PALs production. The
30 composition of reaction species around gas may be changed by altering the content of plasma
31 working gas and plasma streams [243]. Another technique for the selective production of reactive
32 species is gas bubbles in liquids with various working gases [244]. Recently, an open-air
33 discharge in various types of discharge (spark discharge and fluid discharge) above liquids
34 without utilizing any extra, or noble working gases will create reactive species in specification

1 to plasma-activated water (PAW) [239]. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that the cytotoxicity
2 of PAW may be eliminated by optimizing plasma parameters and composition by altering the
3 discharge method and again without utilizing working gas or chemical splashing agents with
4 the use of hydrogen peroxide and nitrite as primary reactive species indicators [245]. While the
5 antimicrobial mechanisms of PAW and PTL have been well-characterized in planktonic
6 models and general biochemical assays, there is currently a notable lack of literature directly
7 applying these treatments to complex, implanted-device biofilms. Existing studies on typical
8 implant-colonizing pathogens (e.g., *S. epidermidis*) primarily rely on simple in vitro setups.
9 Consequently, extrapolating the current understanding of PAW/PTL reactive species chemistry
10 to the microenvironment of an in vivo implant biofilm remains a technical challenge and a
11 necessary direction for future research. Several gaps remain for clinical adoption:

- 12 • **Standardization:** The chemical composition and stability of PAW depends heavily on the
13 plasma source and treatment time, requiring standardized protocols.
- 14 • **Dosage Optimization:** Further study is needed to optimize the dose and frequency of
15 application to maximize efficacy.
- 16 • **Stability:** The RONS species in PAW may over time, making immediate use or careful
17 storage necessary.

18 [Table 4](#) comprehensively summarize different types of plasmas and their direct/indirect
19 interaction towards implant-related bacteria forming biofilms. The inferences in the table
20 comments on the plasma resulting in either removal or reducing the concentration of the
21 bacteria. Some findings even inferred the permeating bacterial cells membrane, resulting in
22 DNA damage for bacterial inactivation.

23
24 **Table 4:** Table summarizing direct and indirect interaction of NTP with device/biofilm
25 surfaces with their results/inferences and reference.

26
27

NTP direct interaction with microbes/biofilms										
Plasma source/type	Gas composition & flow	Operating pressure	Power & Voltage	Treatment time	Target organism	Biofilm model	Substrate material	Key biological outcome	Study type	Reference
APPJ	Ar/He mixture	Atmospheric	Not reported	Short exposure	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	Biofilm	Titanium disc	Porosity of the biofilm increases during plasma treatment and enables it to penetrate deeper into the porous biofilm and destroy all bacterial cells.	<i>in-vitro</i>	[246]
APPJ	He/O ₂ (0.5-2%) & N ₂	Atmospheric	Not reported	30 min	<i>S. aureus</i>	Biofilm	Standard coupon	>3 log reduction, inhibited biofilm regeneration capacity	<i>in-vitro</i>	[247]
APPJ	Ar + 1% vol O ₂	Atmospheric	2 – 6 kV _{p-p} , 1.7 MHz, 65 W	60 – 300 s	<i>C. albicans</i> , <i>supragingival plaque</i>	Water only grown biofilm	Extracted teeth/ tap water	89% removal at 300 s; etching of biofilm matrix comparable to sonic brush	<i>ex-vivo</i>	[248]
APPJ	Argon (1.2 L/min)	Atmospheric	10 Kv _{p-p} , 23.5 kHz	5 min	<i>aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	Planctonic PAH	Deionized water	Synergistic action of H ₂ O ₂ and low pH effectively decontaminated pathogens	<i>in-vitro</i>	[249]
APPJ (kINPenMED)	Argon	Atmospheric	Not reported	0 – 240 s	<i>S. aureus</i>	Biofilm (hp100 M)	Wet milieu	Slight bactericidal efficacy under planktonic; no effect on biofilms	<i>in-vitro</i>	[250]
APPJ	He and O ₂	Atmospheric	Not reported	4 to 10 min	<i>B. cereus</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. Coli</i>	Biofilm	Peg lid of Calgary biofilm device	Complete eradication of gram-positive in < 4 min, gram-negative in 10 min	<i>in-vitro</i>	[251]
APPJ	Ar + N ₂	Atmospheric	Low power	3 min	<i>S. aureus</i>	Biofilm	Not reported	78% population reduction within 3 min	<i>in-vitro</i>	[252]

APPJ	He + 0.5% O ₂	Atmospheric	Not reported	2 – 15 min	<i>E. faecalis</i>	7 – day biofilm	Extracted teeth root canal	Effectively reduced CFU compared to conventional PDT treatments	<i>ex-vivo</i>	[253]
APPJ	Ar and Ar + 1% O ₂ (5 slm)	Atmospheric	2 – 6 kV _{P-P} , 1.1 MHz, 3.5 W	5 min	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i>	Biofilm	Microtiter plates	5.41 log reduction (<i>P. aeruginosa</i>), 3.1 log reduction (<i>S. epidermidis</i>)	<i>in-vitro</i>	[254]
DBD & APPJ	Ar + 1% O ₂	Atmospheric	Not reported	Upto 10 min	<i>C. albicans</i>	2-, 7- and 16-day biofilm	Titanium and PMMA discs	Reduced CFU significantly compared to chemical disinfectants (upto log 5 reduction)	<i>in-vitro</i>	[255]
ICP-APPJ	He (20.4 lpm) & N ₂ (0.135 lpm)	Atmospheric	100 W (13.56 MHz)	1-30 min	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Continuous culture biofilm	Hydroxyapatite and glass	Impacted biofilm architecture and cell culture ability; decreased matrix adhesiveness	<i>in-vitro</i>	[256]
APPJ	He + 2 % O ₂	Atmospheric	6 kV, 1 kHz, 0.7 W	5 min	<i>E. faecalis</i>	6 – day monolayer	Hydroxyapatite discs	93.1% kill rate, no intact bacteria discernible vis SEM	<i>in-vitro</i>	[257]
Surface-DBD	Air	Atmospheric	Not reported	7 min preparation + 15 min exposure	<i>E. coli</i>	Planktonic	NaCl	Complete bacteria inactivation (>= 7 log)	<i>in-vitro</i>	[258]
DBD	Air	Atmospheric	High voltage 100	5 min	<i>E. coli</i>	Surface	PET film	99.99% germicidal efficiency via membrane etching	<i>in-vitro</i>	[259]

Low pressure plasma	O ₂	Low pressure	Variable	Not reported	<i>B. subtilis</i>	Spores	Various polymer surfaces	Spore destruction via synergy of UV photons and reactive species	<i>in-vitro</i>	[260]
RF plasma/DC glow discharge	Air, N ₂ , O ₂ , Ar	Low pressure	80 W	120 s	Not available (focus on biocompatibility)	Not available	LDPE	Improved wettability and biocompatibility via chitosan immobilization	<i>ex-vivo</i>	[261]
MW-induced plasma	Ar	Atmospheric	Microwave (2.45 GHz)	< 20 s	Gram positive and gram negative	Biofilm	Not reported	Biofilms removed in < 20 s; planktonic bacteria inhibited in 5 s	<i>in-vitro</i>	[262]
HV-CAP	Air/O ₂ -containing	Atmospheric	80 kV (RMS)	15 – 120 s	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	Planktonic	In package	<i>E. coli</i> inactivated by cell leakage; <i>S. aureus</i> by intracellular damage	<i>in-vitro</i>	[263]
CAP	Not reported	Atmospheric	Not reported	Sub-lethal	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Biofilm	Not reported	Sub-lethal CAP increased sensitivity to anti-microbial activity via oxidative stress	<i>in-vitro</i>	[264]
CAP (Piezo brush PZ3)	Air	Atmospheric	~50 kHz, 8 V	Not reported	Periodontal pathogens	Multi-species biofilm	Titanium/dentin	Antibacterial activity against multi species biofilm	<i>in-vitro</i>	[265]
SDBD	Air (0.5 slm)	Atmospheric	3 kV/10 kHz (SDBD-A), 8 kV/30 kHz (SDBD-B)	600 s	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i>	Biofilm	Polycarbonate discs	High antimicrobial efficacy compared to CHx; < 150 s safe for tissues	<i>in-vitro</i>	[266]

Multi pin to plate DBD	Ambient air and He (2 slm)	Atmospheric	12-18 kV, 360 Hz	Varies	<i>E. coli</i>	Suspended in liquid	Aqueous liquids	1 log reduction; inactivation combined with RONS and low pH	<i>in-vitro</i>	[267]
Surface microdischarges	Air	Atmospheric	HV	5 – 15 min	<i>C. albicans</i>	Biofilm	Heat sensitive material surface	Contact time inactivation achieved >=3 log reduction in CFU/mL	<i>in-vitro</i>	[268]
DC corona discharges	Air	Atmospheric	HV-DC	5-10 min	<i>Streptococci</i>	Biofilm	Characterized tooth	Up to 3 logs reduction in 10 min enhanced with electrospray	<i>ex-vivo</i>	[269]
NTP indirect interaction with microbes/biofilms										
Plasma source/type	Gas composition & flow	Operating pressure	Power & Voltage	Treatment time	Target organism	Biofilm model	Substrate material	Key biological outcome	Study type	Reference
Pulsed DC hollow cathode PECVD	Precursor gases (Ge dopant)	Low pressure	Not reported	Deposition	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	Biofilm	316L stainless steel	90% reduction in <i>P. aeruginosa</i> biomass, disruption of cellular wall and component leakage	<i>in-vitro</i>	[270]
PIII	Mg+ and Ag+ ions	Low pressure	20 kV	Deposition	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	Adhesion assay	Titanium surface	Mg/Ag coating balanced osteogenic and antibacterial properties; 7-10% higher efficacy	<i>in-vitro</i> & <i>in-vivo</i>	[271]
PIII (pulsed cathodi	Zn+	0.1 Pa	20 kV	20-80 m deposition	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>	Osteoblast interaction	Titanium surface	Promoted osteogenesis and early phase osseointegration; antibacterial effect	<i>in-vitro</i> &	[272]

arc plasma)									<i>in-vivo</i>	
PIII	N ₂ ⁺	0.8 Pa	20 kV & 200 Hz	Short pulsed 20 us	Pathogens	Surface adhesion	Soft elastic polyurethane	Increased surface energy; bound fibrinogen surface became hard and wrinkled	<i>in-vitro</i>	[273]
PIII	C ₂ & N ₂	Low pressure	40 kV	6 – 18 min	Host cells (<i>BMSCs</i>)	Cell adhesion & osteogenesis	Zirconium (3Y-ZrO ₂)	Introduced nitrogen functional groups without altering bulk stability; significantly <i>BMSC</i> adhesion, proliferation, and osteogenic differentiation	<i>in-vitro</i>	[274]
FE-DBD	Air	Atmospheric	120 V, 0.13 W/cm ²	15 – 120 s	<i>Methicillin resistant S. aureus</i>	Planktonic and biofilm (surface colonies)	Solid agar plates and artificial surfaces	Sterilized all the biofilm forms of the pathogens under 120 s; induced membrane lipid peroxidation and oxidative DNA damage	<i>in-vitro</i>	[275]
Microbubble reactor (DBD)	Air	Atmospheric	4 kV, 40 W	15 min	Multispecies pathogenic biofilms	Summer green aquatic biofilm	Artificial surfaces and living tissue (fish skin)	Reduced existing pathogenic biofilm load by ~83%; prevented new biofilm formation via RONS (especially NO) delivery	<i>in-vitro</i> & <i>in-vivo</i>	[276]

9. Plasma Chemistry Influence on Infection Control

The chemical composition of NTP is complex and several distinct reactive agents are involved in inactivating microbial targets, individually or synergistically. The composition and effectiveness of NTP is generally determined by the design and operational system characteristics of the device, such as gas composition, flow rate, temperature, voltage and frequency [277-279]. NTP is a very good source of electrons and positive or negative ions, free radicals, stable conversion products, excited atoms and molecules and UV photons [280]. Active forms of oxygen molecules and atoms, that are ROS), such as atomic oxygen O , singlet oxygen 1O_2 , superoxide anion O_2^- , ozone O_3 ; RNS such as atomic nitrogen N , nitrogen molecule N_2 , nitric oxide NO . H_2O+OH , $\cdot OH$ radical and H_2O_2 reactive species generated in the most frequently used plasma sources [281]. The specific processes of bacterial inactivation mediated by NTP are currently being examined although many products have been shown to have a role. These products include radiation from ROS, RNS, UV and charged particles during the plasma gas phase. Bacterial inactivation is thought to be involving ROS, ozone, atomic oxygen, singlet oxygen, superoxide, peroxide and hydroxyl radicals [282,283].

Most bacteria are regarded to be sensitive to ROS species, in particular, anaerobes. Degradation of bacterial cell wall via oxygen species or atomic oxygen and nitrogen oxide causes local damage potentially through cytoplasmic membrane, protein and DNA strands oxidation [212]. The ROS source greatly reduces oxidized *E. coli* DNA damage. Joshi et al. have demonstrated that the singlet oxygen and hydrogen peroxide species are responsible for the disruption of membrane through lipid peroxidation [284]. Furthermore, inactivation effectiveness may increase with ROS and RNS, which has shown that oxygen mixture is significant for working gases. The addition of 2% oxygen in nitrogen (carrier gas) was shown by Puresh Kumar et al. to produce nitric oxides which greatly increased the inactivation effect [283]. Optical emission spectroscopy has verified the presence of these reactive species. Charge-excited species, electrons and ion on a cell wall can break up chemical links, causing erosion through etching, erosion development, and membrane holes which induce deeper penetration into a bacterial cell [281]. The fragility of the cell wall compared to gram-positive species with a thicker membrane structure, is said to be simpler for erosion inactivation in gram negative bacteria [285]. However, due to increased intracellular ROS level, the intracellular damage in Gram-positive bacteria was evident [203]. The action of excited plasma species, which are commonly categorized in literature as direct and indirect as shown in [Figure 7 & 11](#). However, such plasma induced reactive species is the another key factor in the mechanical rupture of the bacterial cell membrane [279]. In the indirect design of treatment, distance or metal mesh is used

1 to avoid direct contact with samples of charged particles [286]. Charged particles can build up
 2 on the surface with direct contact, leading to electrostatic tension. The tensile strength of the
 3 cell membrane may be overcome, by changing its external structure morphology [287,288].
 4 Perforation of the cell membrane due to etching improves the diffusion of secondary reactive
 5 species that may develop within the cell during the plasma discharge. Etching produces a
 6 breakdown of the bonds, especially in hydrocarbon compounds, due to the interaction between
 7 the excited atoms / radicals and organic components. This, in turn, leads to the creation of
 8 molecular fragments and volatile excited species exposed to cells, which cause morphologic
 9 alterations from cell-size reduction to deep channel appearances in the cell. Complete cell is
 10 destroyed. Graves presented a model emphasizing the relevance of the adaptive response of the
 11 biological systems, noting that biological systems may be responding to plasma reactive
 12 species across a longer time-space exposure scale [289].
 13

14
 15 Figure 11: The direct and indirect NTP interaction involving several pathways in cellular
 16 disruption such as metabolic reactions, oxidative phosphorylation, DNA leakage/damage due
 17 to oxidative stress, UV radiation, uptake of foreign materials, cell membrane modification due
 18 to low pH, most internal pathways involving due to plasma RONS (Created using
 19 Biorender.com).

1
2 In a recent study done by Ghimire et. al. the H₂O₂ and PAW bactericidal activity was
3 evaluated against the planktonic cultures gram-negative *P. aeruginosa* and Gram-positive *S.*
4 *aureus* these are the two frequent pathogens found in most chronic illnesses. First, the use of
5 standard doses of 0.87–55.62 mM for bacterial inhibition was tested. The optical density at 600
6 nm (OD₆₀₀) of bacterial suspension was measured for bacterial growth. In the range of
7 1.74mM to >0.86 mM and 13.90 mM to >6.95 mM respectively for *P. aeruginosa* and *S.*
8 *aureus*, a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), which indicates the lowest concentration
9 of a "drug" that may suppress bacterial growth [290].

10 The role of PAW species in inhibiting the microbes is discussed further to understand
11 the NTP chemistry. The presence of molecules of water vapor impacts significantly the plasma
12 production of the [•]OH, which recombines to H₂O₂. The process gas contains water molecules
13 that promote the formation of [•]OH at the plasma discharge centre. The [•]OH generation in the
14 plasma effluent is also facilitated by water vapor in ambient air. The gas utilized in this
15 investigation is an impurity of 99.9 % argon containing moisture (always ≤ 0.5 ppm) and
16 nitrogen (to ≤ 0.5 ppm), according to gas supplier (BOC) [291]. It was finally concluded from
17 this work that the bactericidal activities of H₂O₂ could be improved by acidified NO₂⁻ in low
18 pH PAW [292]. Although the bactericidal killings at these planktonic bacterial tests need less than
19 1 mM of H₂O₂ in PAW, it is probable that such higher concentrations of H₂O₂ in PAW would
20 be needed to remove these bacteria in the biofilm state.

21 In another study by Jeong et al. the use of N₂/O₂ gas mix environment was used with
22 plasma discharge on the bacterial suspension to find the efficacy of inactivation by various
23 induced plasma chemistry. The content of nitrite is discovered to have been the determinant
24 for the bactericidal differentiation of plasma discharge of various gases. The dissolution of
25 nitrogen oxides (NO_x) created during the gas phase is used for plasma treatment to produce
26 nitrite and nitrates in solution. From the release of carrier gas air, various plasma reactive
27 species are created, including atomic species (N, O) and the excited states species react further
28 with one another in order to make NO in substantial quantities through numerous basic
29 processes [293]. The generated NO can be further oxidized to NO₂ and other NO_x and then
30 dissolved into the solution, together with acidity of the solution, to form nitrite and nitrate [241].
31 The solution pH decrease is based on the concentration of nitrite and nitrate generated in it. In
32 the case of N₂, the necessary O for NO production might be caused by the dissociation of water
33 in or on the surface of the bulk liquid, or O₂ dissolved in liquid.

In plasma-treated N₂ water nitrite/nitrate is therefore identified, while the concentration in air-plasma-treated water is almost half that. Mechanism for inactivation of bacteria through nitrate generated nitrite reacts to a powerful peroxyxynitrite (O=NOO⁻; pKa = 6.8) (reaction 7 and 8) with H₂O₂ in acidified media [294].

There is a substantial dependency on the current form of peroxyxynitrite (O=NOOH and O=NOO⁻). For example, at pH 7.4 approximately 80 % peroxyxynitrite will be formed as O=NOO⁻, but at pH 6.2 it will be formed as O=NOOH up to 80 % peroxyxynitrite. During the air and N₂ plasma treatment, the pH value fell significantly such that peroxyxynitrite is predominantly O=NOOH⁺, O=NOOH and O=NOO⁻ to permeate cell membranes are quite different in strength, reactivity and capacity. O=NOOH is a lot more responsive than O=NOO⁻. They can be subjected to proton-catalyzed homolysis. NO₂ and [•]OH are relatively stable in about 30% of yield, respectively two oxidizers and nitrates/hydroxylating species. O=NOOH may reach to the cell membrane at a pace much quicker than its breakdown routes with simple diffusion, whereas anionic membranes can trap with O=NOO⁻. Consequently, the membrane does not present a major barrier to O=NOOH diffusion inside or between cells, while it is an essential barrier between the cell and the outside environment. O=NOOH, specifically, is extremely bactericidal in peroxyxynitrite and can inactivate *E. coli* as a direct consequence of its reactivity and oxidation potential. It has the ability to destroy bacterial interactions with many targets, such as protein changes, lipid oxidation and DNA damage. Active oxidation of nitrate induces NO₂ and [•]OH. Peroxyxynitrite has also been found to be a powerful cause of DNA damage, including rupture of the strand and alteration of the base. The aim was chosen to detect both the extracellular (membrane) and intracellular (DNA) damage caused by plasma peroxyxynitrite. Compared to O₂ plasma, air plasma has caused significantly more membrane-pierced cells and membrane damage, suggesting that a significant portion of membrane damage to plasma-derived peroxyxynitrite is necessary for bacterial inactivation. The double stranded DNA (dsDNA) concentration in *E. coli* was reduced following air plasma treatment, measured using SYBR green I, whereas O₂ plasma had reduced the dsDNA somewhat, which also shows that DNA was an important target for air-plasma peroxyxynitrite [295]. It is apparent that N₂ plasma, followed by air plasma, induced the most hydroxyl-radical, with O₂ plasma showed the least bactericidal efficacy. We therefore conclude that although if transient species such as hydroxyl

1 radicals play a part during plasma treatment in directly bacterial inactivation it is still not an
 2 important reason why various gas discharge plasmas have varied bactericidal activities.

3 Sysolyatina et. al., investigated inhibition of *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* by
 4 atmospheric pressure plasma with air as carrier gas and by positive and negative corona
 5 discharge. It was observed due to UV⁺ reactive species (R) + electrons (E) bactericidal effect
 6 for both the microbes with both the coronas were identical. The R agents are driven by reactive
 7 NTP product such as atoms, metastables, radicals, electrically and vibrationally stimulated
 8 molecules, i.e., neutral reactive species of short and long lived such as $O_2(1D)$, O_3 , NO ,
 9 HO_2 , H_2O_2 , $\cdot OH$, etc. In reality, almost every radical (except for O and O_3) in a native cell
 10 exists constantly [296]. All radicals in the cell usually have a dynamic equilibrium, i.e. they
 11 emerge continuously and disappear, maintaining their average concentration at the necessary
 12 level. Table 5 shows the quantity, certain characteristics and typical concentrations of most
 13 significant intracellular radicals in gaseous, NTP at atmospheric pressure [298].

14
 15 **Table 5:** Concentration of observed species in gaseous NTP and properties of most important
 16 radicals generated inside cell [297].

Name of species	Sym bol	Concent ration in NTP (cm ⁻³)	Concent ration in contact cell [mol L ⁻¹ , cm ⁻³]	Half period of life in cell (T=3kT/C) [s]	Properties
Molecular oxygen (weak oxidant)	O ₂	6x10 ¹⁷ –6x10 ¹⁸ (depends on pressure)	[10 ⁻⁶], 6x10 ¹⁴	>10 ²	Has a good ability to diffuse through bio-membranes like NO, N ₂ , and CO ₂

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) Superoxide	O_2^-	10^{10} – 10^{12}	$[10^{-11}]$, 6×10^9	10^{-6}	Does not penetrate through bio-membranes; can react with NO to form ONO_2^-
Hydroperoxyl	HO_2	3×10^{12} – 3×10^{14}	$[10^{-11}]$, 6×10^9	10^{-8}	Has ability to diffuse; may be an initiator of lipid peroxidation
Singlet Oxygen	$O_2(^1\Delta)$	3×10^{12} – 10^{15}	$[10^{-11}]$, 6×10^9	10^{-6}	Highly reactive; has ability to diffuse; causes cell death
Hydrogen Peroxide	H_2O_2	$<10^{12}$ (calculated)	$[10^{-8}]$, 6×10^{10}	10^2	Has ability to diffuse for a long distance; delivers OH to the membrane structures and internal cell components due to reaction with metal ions
Hydroxyl	$\cdot OH$	10^{11} – 10^{12}	$[10^{-11}]$, 6×10^9	10^{-9}	Extremely reactive; able to diffuse only for one-two of its diameters; initiates the chain reactions of lipid oxidation in the lipid layer of the cell membranes
Reactive nitrogen species (RNS) Nitric oxide	NO	10^{13} – 10^{14}	$[10^{-6}]$, 6×10^{14}	0.1–6.4	Has a good ability to diffuse for a long distance; can be bactericidal directly as well as by conversion to ONO_2
Peroxynitrite	$ONOO^-$	3×10^9 – 3×10^{10}	$< [10^{-6}]$, $< 6 \times 10^{14}$	1–2	Strong oxidant; does not penetrate through biomembranes; has ability to diffuse for long distance. ONO_2^- initiates cell death

10. Conclusions and future scope

Medical devices, surgery implants and wounds offer appealing colonization sites for highly adaptable organisms and hence an elevated risk of infection. Although the potential for antimicrobial materials to lower infections is evident, there is considerable criticism that antimicrobial resistance to agents employed is being developed. Resistance towards antibiotics and phagocytes is currently an urgent worry. Another important difficulty is the recurrence of infections following treatment. According to the time of diagnosis, the infection incidence rate decreases with time after the implantation. Late instances may be either direct, or in some circumstances, bloodstream seeding infections.

The most notable approach for the eradication and prevention of mixed-species biofilms is the NTP, which produces many distinct species of active components to perform microbiocide mechanisms. NTP can deconstruct the mixed-species biofilm matrix and also destroy microbial cells have been verified by accumulated research. NTP can be created in the water supply system, food industry and medical practices as an effective tool for mixed biofilms. A more thorough knowledge of the biofilm phenotype and surface modification of the medical implant, combined with the molecules that work as quorum quenchers/inhibit and prevent the development of bacterial adhesion and its associated infections, is the key to the success of antibiofilm methods. Comprehensive investigations in recent years demonstrate clearly the potential nature of this technology in the eradication of medical biofilms. However, the creation of a strong platform that can take use of this technology has been a long-standing unmet requirement. The development of viable NTP devices is therefore necessary if this technology is not only restricted to *in-vitro* and a few *in-vivo* investigations, but to transform the paradigm into a world of decontamination/sterilization. In order to offer a unique barrier against biofilm infection, further research should be strengthened and examined into new control techniques for biofilm and different creative ways to surface modification for preventing the infection of bacteria in medical implants. A strategic roadmap is given below for future use of NTP for experimental and translational priorities in the field of plasma medicine. This section would serve the guide to the community towards resolving barriers preventing NTPs clinical adoption.

10.1 Standardization and regulatory compliance:

A significant obstacle to advancing in clinical applications is the absence of standardized dosimetry and documentation. Future studies should prioritize the widespread adoption of

1 frameworks like the German DIN SPEC 91315 ("General requirements for medical plasma
2 sources")^[298]. This guideline sets forth essential criteria for the physical and biological
3 assessment of cold atmospheric pressure plasma sources, necessitating precise measurements
4 of gas temperatures, UV exposure, leakage currents, and output of reactive species^[299].

5 Moving away from vague "treatment times" reporting is crucial. Instead, emphasis should be
6 placed on reporting the exact fluxes of essential reactive species ($\cdot\text{OH}$ or O_3) per unit area of
7 biofilm volume. Developing real-time sensors for plasma dosimetry on-site is a critical
8 technological goal. Moreover, navigating through strict regulatory frameworks set by
9 organizations such as the FDA (US), EMA (Europe), and PMDA (Japan) is vital for the path
10 to clinical acceptance^[300]. Future priorities should concentrate on providing necessary safety
11 data for Premarket Approval (PMA) or 510(k) clearance, including thorough biocompatibility
12 assessments (ISO 10993) to confirm that plasma emissions do not produce harmful byproducts
13 when interacting with intricate biological tissues^[300].

14 10.2 Advanced and clinically relevant biofilm models:

15 Presently, the majority of *in-vitro* NTP studies use static microtiter plate assays lasting 24 to
16 48 hours on flat polystyrene or titanium surfaces. These basic models fail to replicate the
17 complex conditions found in actual medical implants within the human body, such as
18 hemodynamic shear stress, host-protein films, and intricate 3D structures. Future experimental
19 priorities should mandate the use

- 20 • **Dynamic flow bioreactors** to imitate high shear stress environments like vascular or
21 urinary systems.
- 22 • **Coculture models** with host immune cells and multi-species biofilms to evaluate
23 selective toxicity and host-tissue tolerance simultaneously.
- 24 • **Testing on complex geometries** like porous orthopedic structures to assess plasma
25 penetration depth and fluid dynamics of plasma species.

26 10.3 Systems biology and multi-omics approaches:

27 As the field transitions beyond traditional germ theory, forthcoming research must embrace the
28 dynamic interactions between host biology, microbiota composition, and biomaterial
29 characteristics^[301]. Incorporating systems biology methods, such as transcriptomics,
30 proteomics, and metabolomics, holds promise in advancing our comprehension of implant-
31 related infections^[302]. Future investigations should prioritize multi-omics profiling to
32 understand how plasma-induced reactive oxygen and nitrogen species influence host immune

1 responses, potentially reshaping an imbalanced, immune-suppressive environment surrounding
2 an infected implant to support bacterial eradication and tissue regeneration^[302].

3 10.4 Synergistic combination therapies:

4 To address the challenges of penetrating mature biofilms and the risk of rapid recolonization,
5 NTP should not be viewed as a standalone treatment^[301]. Future clinical strategies should
6 explore the synergy between NTP and traditional therapies. For instance, NTP can induce
7 sublethal oxidative stress to weaken the EPS matrix, reducing the Minimum Inhibitory
8 Concentration (MIC) needed for antibiotics or localized nanomedicines. Alternatively,
9 plasma treatment can prime a surface before applying anti-adhesion, hydrogen peroxide, or quorum-
10 sensing inhibitors, creating a multifaceted defense mechanism that tackles both immediate
11 decontamination and long-term prevention. A few numbers of authorized, commercially
12 accessible clinical systems are available, and while cold plasma has great therapy potential, it
13 promotes clinical adoption and broader regulatory approval to ensure biological safety. NTPs
14 can offer considerable benefits over traditional bacterial methods as a therapeutic strategy
15 for treatment of microbial biofilms in clinical practice.

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29 **Data Availability:**

30 The preprint copy of this article is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19705453> and
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32

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